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CHARACTERISATION AND MODELLING OF
THE UV-VIS-IR TRANSMISSION OF
MULTILAYER THIN FILM FILTERS FOR
APPLICATIONS IN HIGH ENERGY
ASTROPHYSICS

TESI DI LAUREA DI
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MAGISTRALE

*Too often we underestimate the simple fact that
We are given the possibility to think and study freely,
Expressing our virtue, as scientists, to pursue knowledge.
I dedicate this work to the people who fought for this right,
And to everyone whose rights are currently undermined.*

*‘ Peace, progress and human rights are three indissolubly linked aims,
no one of which may be achieved if the others are neglected.’*

—ANDREI SAKHAROV

Abstract

This work deals with the experimental investigation and modelling of the UV-Vis-IR transmission of multilayer thin film filters (MTFFs) designed for Athena, the large space mission selected in 2014 by the European Space Agency (ESA) to study the Cosmic Vision theme ‘Hot and Energetic Universe’. The mission is composed of a large effective area X-ray telescope and two focal plane detectors, the X-ray Integral Field Unit (X-IFU) and the Wide Field Imager (WFI). Both detectors need filters to block non-X-ray radiation, while still ensuring a high X-ray transmission. At the moment the mission is in the B1 definition phase; thus, along with all the satellite systems, the filters need to be properly studied by experimental tests to consolidate their preliminary design. In collaboration with UNIPA and INAF, samples of the designed multi-layered thin film filters are analysed and modelled in the UV-Vis-IR radiation bands, to verify their shielding properties from electromagnetic radiation coming from the environment, from the astrophysical sources within the telescope field-of-view and, particularly for the X-IFU, IR emitted by warm surfaces inside the instrument cryostat. The main objective is to experimentally measure the transmission of the samples with FTIR-MIR and UV/Vis/NIR spectroscopy techniques, in order to characterise them and to develop a proper transmission model in the electromagnetic band of interest, for ultimately assessing instruments’ compliance with the mission’s requirements.

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1 Introduction

It is pleasing to delve into the deep science, theories and phenomena of the universe, far beyond our very eyes. It is as wonderful to understand the science of the technology involved in achieving such understanding. The planning of future space missions is a unique place where these two different sides of the same coin get to unite and collaborate. In these scenarios, the same physics that is used to analyse phenomena billions of parsec away must be applied beforehand to the instruments which can contain features measuring down to tens of nanometres, such as the width of the optical filters analysed in this work. This introduction is useful to understand the main themes of this thesis, whose main objective is to deal with the experimental analysis of optical multilayer thin film filters (MTFFs) for applications in high energy astrophysics X-ray missions, in general, and particularly in ESA's newest selected X-ray mission project *Athena*.

The X-ray observatory *Athena* (Advanced Telescope for High ENergy Astrophysics [1, 2]) is an ESA large class mission designed to pursue ESA's Hot and Energetic Universe science theme [3]. Its purpose is to help answer very important questions of great interest to X-ray astronomy, labelled *Science Goals* by *Athena*'s coordination group, each posing diverse technological challenges and requirements for the mission's scientific payload and the details of which can be found in the proposal paper available online for consultation [4]. Here are some examples of the questions addressed by the mission, relating to all aspects of modern astrophysics and cosmology:

- The formation and evolution of galaxy clusters, and energy and matter's distribution around large-scale dark matter potential wells.
- The evaluation of active galactic nuclei (AGN) energy deposition onto clusters and their interaction with star formation processes.
- The chemical evolution of hot baryons in the intracluster medium (ICM), by probing the effect of supernovae (SN) and stellar or AGN-driven winds.
- Analysis of missing baryons in the warm-hot intergalactic medium at $z < 1 - 2$.
- Probing accreting systems such as supermassive black holes (SMBH) and their disks in strong gravity regimes.

Although these are the primary goals, there are other scientific topics that could have *Athena* involved in the future, such as surveys apt to constrain mass-radii relations for neutron stars, magnetic phenomena in young stars, star-planet interactions both outside and inside our solar system (such as the X-ray emissions of Jupiter or Mars). There are also many

opportunities for multi-messenger events, with the likes of X-ray emissions and temporal evolution of NS-mergers even fainter than in the famous GW170817 [5]. It is clear that the high scientific potential of Athena becomes even more important if the synergies with other facilities and missions simultaneously working are exploited fully. As of the moment, the launch is expected to happen in about 2035, and the mission will be functional together with many facilities already available or under development, such as LIGO+, Advanced Virgo+, LISA (ESA's Laser Interferometer Space Antenna), Ice Cube, KM3Net (Cubic Kilometre Neutrino Telescope), VLT (Very Large Telescope), CTA (Cherenkov Telescope Array) and SKA (Square Kilometre Array), all of which will explore scientific cases via either gravitational waves, neutrinos, visible or infrared light, analogously to Athena with X-rays. The potential science from the collaboration of these observatories will have an impact on future astronomy. Nevertheless, Athena's science goals drive very sharp system requirements on the payload and the utmost care must be put in every single component of the mission, one crucial part of which is the design of optical blocking filters (OBFs) and thermal filters (THFs) whose analysis and description is the main focus of this thesis project.

As the science of thin film filters usage in X-ray astrophysics spans more than 50 years, many of their key aspects have been acquainted with the heritage of past successful and/or still ongoing missions where they have been employed, such as the very first ones adopting imaging telescopes, the Einstein satellite and the EXOSAT mission, all the way to the recent Chandra and XMM-Newton observatories, milestones of the high energy science of the cosmos. In all of these projects, OBFs were crucial in reducing noise at the detectors by absorbing and reflecting away out-of-band radiation, such as UV, visible or IR light from either bright sources or the hot surfaces of the space-crafts, consequently improving the quality of X-ray signals revealed by the detectors. As technology and science made progress during these last decades, so did the projects for new observatories, and Athena itself is a living example that will put multiple pieces of cutting-edge technological hardware to the test. Many are the researchers worldwide working in this huge space project, all of them well determined to assemble exceptional working equipment to achieve the science requirements of the mission. Within the Athena consortium, Italian researchers have different key roles in the science and technology: as an example, the research team of Unipa and INAF-OAPA is responsible for the design and development of the detectors' thin filters.

Although nanometric film optical filters have been employed in space for more than half a century, they need to be continuously probed, their technology well understood, and their performance thoroughly tested, as their requirements for modern science instruments pose a

greater challenge than ever. The thesis aims to describe the current understanding of optical and thermal transmission of MTFs used for high energy astrophysics, to investigate samples of the filters currently designed for Athena via direct use of UV-Vis and IR spectroscopy techniques - in order to aid the validation of the mission's system requirements - and, finally, to develop a reliable model to support the design optimisation. All of the experimental and computational activities involved with this work were executed under the supervision of Prof. M. Barbera (Unipa) and Dr. U. Lo Cicero (INAF-OAPA), along with continuous fruitful exchanges with their INAF/Unipa research group.

The body of work is split into three different parts. The first part is an introduction on the Athena mission, to the technologies of its optics and detectors, and also to the filters currently designed and under investigation. Moreover, a brief outline of the application of thin film filters in some recent X-ray missions is laid out.

The second part is the central experimental part of the thesis, where the investigated filter samples and the employed instrumentation - IR and UV-Vis spectrometers - are described, and the transmission measurements' results are presented.

Lastly, the third part addresses the analysis of data via Python scripts employing the Transfer-Matrix Method and recently published models for the indexes of refraction, all followed by a discussion of the findings, the best-fit parameters obtained and of the statistics. These latter chapters, aided by some appendices guiding through the more technical aspects of the modelling procedures, attempt to give general guidelines for similar case studies of MTFs transmission analyses in the infrared and optical bands.

A conclusion follows, summarising the findings of the work, the skills learned and the implications, also forecasting possible future directions.

Part I

Filters for Athena and other X-ray space missions

This first part is divided into three sections. Firstly, the scientific payload of the Athena mission is described, namely the X-ray telescope and the two focal plane detectors, along with some focus on the electronics and their active measuring parts - important for understanding the required performances of the OBFs/THFs.

Following is a description of the main requirements of the filters and their current design being under development. Then, a brief state of the art of the use of thin film optical filters for some of the most recent and influential X-ray astrophysics missions in the last decades is laid out.

Overall, this part forms the core background for the other more experimental and computational parts of the thesis, introducing to the broad science that the experiments are embedded in. As a disclaimer, all of the following figures describe up-to-date specifications of the mission and detectors, but these can be subject to changes during the current definition phase of the mission.

2 Athena in a nutshell

Athena is the next-generation X-ray observatory of the European Space Agency (ESA)¹, planned to be the sequel to other great observatories such as XMM-Newton and Chandra, and expected to be launched in 2035 in the direction of the Lagrange point L1 of the Sun-Earth system. It is the second large mission of the ESA's Cosmic Vision science program, and it will be dedicated, as mentioned, to study the Hot and Energetic Universe.

Figure 1: Artistic depiction of Athena space observatory. Taken from the gallery artistic views section of the Athena community website [2]. Credit: ESA/IRAP/CNRS/UT3/CNES/Fab&Fab/ACO .

The mission is planned to be the leading observatory in terms of the current technology for X-ray science and data collection, surpassing other X-ray missions either currently working, or planned to be launched such as XRISM (2022), at the same time being on par with the yet proposed NASA Lynx project. As mentioned, Athena's scientific payload is comprised of a single telescope and two detectors in the focal plane, the three of which will provide high effective area, fast and wide-area imaging ability, and a very fine spectral resolution, respectively meeting the key parameters and requirements of the mission.

The telescope will use the new technology of Silicon Pore Optics (SPO)[7] as grazing incidence reflective mirrors. The telescope can be tilted by a movable system that changes the path of the focal beam towards either one of the two detectors fixed at the focal plane. These detectors are the Wide Field Imager (WFI)[8], which is a large format array of Dep-FET active pixels detector with performances similar to a CCD, and the X-ray Integral Field Unit (X-IFU)[9], a cryogenic imaging spectrometer working with an array of transition edge sensor (TES) microcalorimeters. All of these key components of the scientific payload will

¹All of the acronyms regarding the Athena project are listed on the continuously updated page <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/athena/acronyms>, also referenced in bibliography [6]

be further described in the following sections.

Athena's large effective area, exceeding by order of magnitudes that in any existing mission, truly defines its strengths and it is made possible by the SPO mirrors. Figures 2 and 3 compare the expected effective area of the Athena detectors to that of other instruments on board other X-ray observatories, illustrating the superiority of the former.

Figure 2: Comparison between Athena's X-IFU effective area and that of other X-ray spectrometers in various missions, either operating (XMM-Newton/Newton RGS, Chandra/HETG), planned (XRISM/Resolve) or proposed (Arcus). Taken from the gallery X-IFU section of the Athena website [2].

Figure 3: Effective area comparison between Athena/WFI (with or without the Filter Wheel Optical Blocking Filter), and the corresponding XMM-Newton/EPIC-pn and Chandra/ACIS-I. Taken from the gallery WFI section of the Athena website [2].

To satisfy the performance requirements of high effective area and low noise levels in the detected signals, both detectors must be shielded from unwanted light signals, such as thermal radiation (IR) coming from the various warm surfaces in the spacecraft and UV-Vis light that might come from very bright astrophysical sources. Hence, the proper design and testing of OBFs/THFs are of paramount importance to the success of the mission. The responsibility of the filter design and development, both for the X-IFU and the WFI, is held mainly by the team of researchers of UNIPA and INAF-OAPA in Palermo. A sub-set of Filter Wheel (FW) filters is a responsibility of the University of Geneva in collaboration with the team of Palermo.

In the following sections, the most important characteristics of the instruments on board the Athena mission will be assessed. The filters designed by the team and their requirements will be detailed in section 3.

2.1 The telescope and the Silicon Pore Optics technology

The Athena telescope is of utmost importance to the mission's thriving. With a 12 m focal length, it is required to provide a collecting **effective area** of 1.4 m^2 at 1 keV and of 0.25 m^2 at 10 keV, and a Half Energy Width (HEW) **angular resolution** of $5''$ for on-axis observations and at least $10''$ for sources with $25'$ off-axis radius, at energies $< 7 \text{ keV}$. In addition, the instrument **field of view** provided by the mirrors is expected to be a diameter of $40'$, and these specifications are enabled by the technology of Silicon Pore Optics (SPO) developed directly by ESA and Cosine Measurement Systems.

The SPO technology was proposed in 2002 and it was considered a lighter substitute for the different kinds of technologies used in other missions with the likes of monolithic shells (i.e. Chandra), replicated shells (XMM-Newton) and thin foils (Hitomi) [10]. The SPO has come to a readiness level high enough to become the basis of Athena, and it relies on the by-products of the semiconductor industry, i.e. high-quality silicon wafers. These are polished to reduce their surface roughness to about 0.1 nm, the level required to properly reflect X-rays, and then they are cut into plates and processed physically and chemically, via wedging, ribbing, and stacking, to obtain an optical module. The wedging is particularly important to make Wolter-I type [11] optics with the mirrors making precise angles one with respect to another, allowing the double reflection of X-rays towards a focal point. The whole manufacturing process is summarised in figure 4, which also depicts the ending result, a mirror module.

Figure 4: Process flow and end product of the manufacturing of SPO modules. Left: Scheme of the process flow starting from the top, with the silicon wafer, to the bottom end product, silicon stacks co-aligned with arc-second accuracy. Credit: M. Bavdaz [12]. Right: An Athena mirror module, consisting of 2x2 stacks of 35 plates. The pores, giving the technology its name, are given by the space in between two adjacent mirrors and two adjacent ribs. Credit: ESA

The telescope itself will be made of ~ 600 modules assembled circularly with an overall diameter of 2.5 m, and its functionality is based on the conical approximation of a Wolter I geometry [10]. Also, a defocussing option will be available for observing very bright sources, by shifting the mirror along the optical axis away from the focal position by 35 mm. A depiction of the double reflection onto a Wolter I geometry for X-ray focusing and an on-axis plane projection of what the Athena telescope will look like with its optical modules are given in figure 5.

More detailed accounts of the Athena X-ray optics development and accurate representations of the optical modules and their geometry are left to the specialised literature [7, 10, 12]. Having introduced the telescope and the main characteristics of SPO, it is time to also introduce the specifications of the two detectors and the technologies behind them.

2.2 The Wide Field Imager

The WFI (Wide-Field Imager) is the spectral-imaging camera for Athena that will provide the mission with fast surveying capabilities along with discrete spectroscopy insights, currently being developed by a consortium of 10 ESA members and NASA, led by MPE.

Figure 5: Exemplification of double reflection of X-rays off of a Wolter 1 geometry optics such as in the optical modules of Athena, and a representative cross-sectional depiction of the telescope. Signals are deflected towards the focal plane where the detector(s) reside. Credit: V.V. Lider [13]

Its key performance requirements are: an energy **resolution** of ≤ 170 eV at 6 keV, a large **field-of-view** of $40' \times 40'$ with a **pixel size** of $2.2'' \times 2.2''$ ($130 \times 130 \mu\text{m}^2$), an **energy range** of 0.2 – 15 keV, a **count rate capability** of ~ 1 Crab, that is $2.4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and, at last, an upper limit for the particle-induced **non-X-ray background** of $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cts / s / cm}^2 / \text{keV}$ in the 2 – 10 keV radiation band. These requirements are accomplished by the detector components, a Large Detector Array (LDA) of active DEPLETED Field Effect Transistor (DEPFET) pixel sensors arranged in a 2×2 mosaic of matrices 512×512 pixels wide, accompanied by a secondary defocussed Fast Detector (FD) chip made of 64×64 pixels, optimised for the fast readout of very bright sources with luminosity up to 10 Crab. The DEPFET arrays and the electronics are expected to operate at the nominal temperature of $\leq 60^\circ\text{C}$, and the detailed procedure in which the signals are detected and processed is described in ref.[4]. The LDA and the FD chips, defining the WFI, are represented in figure 6.

The WFI characteristics, compounded with the high effective area of the telescope (figure 3 of section 2), are the essence of its great potential. To guarantee a low level of background noise and particles, the detector is surrounded by a graded-Z shield whose purpose is to avoid having fluorescence lines hit the instrument. Alongside this shield, a two-fold action of a thin aluminium coating on the detector itself along with a thin film filter (mounted on the related FW) is needed to further block UV and visible light which would degrade the energy resolution of the detector. An overview of the WFI instrument and its subsystems is given in figure 7, though greater details on the instrumentation and its readiness level can be found in the paper [8].

The feasibility of a launch with the WFI-FW kept in atmospheric pressure - without the

Figure 6: Representation of the WFI with its 4 chips and the fast detector chip. Credits: MPE and WFI team

Figure 7: Drawing of the WFI with its main subsystems. Displayed, from top to bottom, the electronics for signal processing and filtering mounted on the Primary Structure, the metal shield surrounding both the large array detector and the fast detector, the FW, the light baffle and the ICPU (Instrument Control and Power Unit). Taken from the Nuggets section of the Athena community website [2] Credits: Arne Rau, MPE and WFI team

need for a vacuum enclosure - was studied and assessed successfully in 2019 during acoustic load tests, which was an important point for the technology readiness level [14, 15]. The filter, along with the other shielding components, has the purpose to suppress visible photons to the order of 10^{-7} . These requirements and the design of the filters will be addressed in section 3.

2.3 The X-ray Integral Field Unit

The X-IFU (X-ray Integral Field Unit) is the high resolution spectrometer that will give Athena the ability to perform spatially resolved high resolution X-ray spectroscopy. It will be provided by an international consortium led by France (IRAP, CNES), Italy and Netherlands, with contributions from 9 other ESA member states, Japan and the United States.

The instrument will have the following properties: a **resolution** of 2.5 eV at energies ≤ 7 keV, with a 5' diameter effective **field-of-view**, an absorber **pixel size** of $5'' \times 5''$ ($\sim 250 \times 250 \mu\text{m}^2$), a working **energy range** of 0.2 – 12.0 keV, a **count rate capability** of 10 mCrab - up to 1 Crab thanks to the mirror defocussing and with degraded energy resolution (≤ 10 eV) - while the expected **time resolution** is 10 μs and, again, the **non-X-ray background** would be at most 5×10^{-3} cts / s / cm^2 / keV in the 2 – 10 keV radiation band. These properties will be granted by the X-IFU components: a hexagonal array of ~ 2400 pixels of molybdenum gold (Mo/Au) TES sensors coupled to absorbers made of bismuth and gold, operating at ≤ 100 mK thanks to a 50 mK thermal bath, along with ingenious cold electronics. A glimpse of the X-IFU detector and its Focal Plane Assembly (FPA) is shown in figure 8, albeit greater details about the hexagonal shaped-detector are found in the gallery X-IFU section of the Athena community website [2]. The principle behind the functionality

Figure 8: A schematic depiction of the X-IFU's Focal Plane Assembly (FPA) inside the cryogenic and dewar shells. The relative positions of the active sensor, the electronics, the shields and the connectors are pointed. Credits: ESA/SRON

of the detector is that the TES is put at the temperature between its superconducting state and its normal state while having a strong thermal link to the absorber: as an X-ray photon is

being absorbed, the TES undergoes a jump in temperature and electrical resistance, the rise of which is promptly detected using a low noise amplifier chain that includes Superconducting Quantum Interference Devices (SQUIDs). This read-out chain of events and the type of readout channels are described in more detail in the proposal paper [4].

To ensure that the instrument works properly at the incredibly low temperatures of less than 100 mK mentioned above, a nested cryogenic chain encompassing the detector is needed, called Detector Cooling System (DCS). This full cryogenic system is illustrated in figure 9, where the nominal temperature for each vessel from the outside to the inside is 200 K, 100 K, 30 K, and then inside the FPA the temperatures reach 2 K and, at last, ~ 50 mK.

Figure 9: A schematic description of the X-IFU cryostat DCS, with its different mechanical coolers and thermal shields. Thin film filters allocations spots are also shown. Credits: D. Barret [9], CNES and X-IFU team

Thermal and optical filters are needed to protect the cold detector. They have to be light enough to ensure a high X-ray transmission, while also being able to attenuate infrared radiation emitted by warm surfaces of the instrument and spacecraft to reduce the detector's Photon Shot Noise (PSN) - the fluctuation of energy deposited by photons due to their discrete nature and random statistical fluctuation of arrival times. Equally important is for the filters to be bulky enough to resist the launch vibrations and the static differential pressure of the different vessels at the working regime. Therefore, it is particularly important that the design

of the filters takes into consideration the different working temperatures, as well as other aspects of the instrument. The status of the technology development of the X-IFU can be found in the related literature [16, 17].

The following sections introduce the requirements of the thermal and optical thin filters for Athena and the current design proposed by the UNIPA/INAF team, with a brief description of the state of the art of thin filter employment in X-ray space missions. These two sections pave the way to the chapters where the experimental analysis of the filters is described.

3 The filters of the Athena focal plane detectors

The main requirements driving the design and development of the Athena filters derive from the mission science requirements which slightly evolve during the mission development until the end of phase B. An in-depth discussion of the requirements of the filters is in the references by Barbera et al. [14, 17], where most of the following pictures are taken from. During the oncoming disquisitions, some of the performed experiments on filter samples aimed at verifying compliance with the requirements will be quoted explicitly.

3.1 The X-IFU thermal and optical blocking filters

A stack of 5 thermal filters (THFs) and a selectable optical blocking filter (OBF) mounted on a FW are presently the baseline for the X-IFU [9]. The main requirements of these filters are listed as follows:

- The **soft X-ray transmission** of the filters needs to be maximised. The X-ray transmission upper bounds for the THFs stack are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: X-ray transmission requirements on the stack of thermal filters to be compatible with the performance of the X-IFU detector

Energy (keV)	THFs Stack Transmission
0.35	0.21
1.0	0.76
7.0	0.90
9.5	0.90

An experimental analysis of a few filter samples to also verify the compliance with the X-ray transmission requirements can be found in Puccio et al. [18].

- The **IR** and **UV-Vis attenuation** needs to be high in order to keep the TES array properly operating at ~ 100 mK, thus without adding significant heat load by radiation, and keeping the PSN contribution to the energy resolution budget of the detector lower than 0.2 eV FWHM to not degrade the energy resolution of the instrument. This part is mainly the concern of this thesis.
- **RF attenuation:** The filters shall attenuate the Radio Frequencies coming from the telemetry and spacecraft operation to reduce electromagnetic interferences (EMI) on TES and SQUID electronics. The RF attenuation should be greater than 30 dB, in the frequency range 30 MHz – 18 GHz, on two of the THFs mounted on cryostat shields that work as Faraday cages. The experimental tests of this particular property are described by Lo Cicero et al. [19].
- The filters need to protect the detector from **particle and molecular contamination** from the satellite environment and to minimise the deposit on top of the filter surfaces which would deteriorate the sensitivity at low energies. In the current baseline, the outer filter in the stack shall be heated up at a temperature of the order of 320 K to minimise contamination [20].

Along with these, the filters will have to withstand a differential pressure of $\lesssim 1$ mbar, other than surviving the severe vibration loads during launch.

The instrument's THFs set consists of 5 separate units each with a different size and distance from the focal plane - in accordance with the DCS design described in fig. 9. Each filter is a bilayer made of 30 nm of aluminium and 45 nm of polyimide, or Al – 30/PI – 45. For short, the aluminium reflects IR radiation and guarantees also the correct RF attenuation at frequencies larger than 6 GHz, whilst the polyimide gives robustness to the structure and absorbs in the UV: these aspects are covered at greater length in the experimental sections of the thesis.

The filters, including the small filter samples investigated in this work, are manufactured by LUXEL Corp., and the polyimide (PI) here mentioned is described by the chemical formula of its monomer being $C_{22}H_{10}N_2O_4$ (provided by the manufacturer): more on the history of polyimide applications is detailed in section 4.

The X-IFU THFs' design is described in figure 10 which also shows the working temperature of each part and a picture example of a filter structure.

Each filter is named THFX, with X being the temperature of the shield on which it is mounted. The name THF0, for simplicity, refers to the coldest filter working at ~ 50 mK. All

Figure 10: On the upper-left, a schematic view of the five thermal filters (THFs) with respect to the focal plane detector in proper distance scale. On the lower left, a picture of an Al – 30/PI – 45 filter sample with a passivated Au plated BeCu mesh. On the right are shown the locations of the THFs inside a schematic drawing of the DCS, and some of the major X-IFU parts are also pointed out. Credits: Unipa/INAF team

of the filters will be provided with a mesh designed to improve their mechanical robustness and in some cases provide RF attenuation at frequencies below 6 GHz. For the four hotter THFs (THF2, THF30, THF100, THF300), the mesh is made of a beryllium-copper (BeCu) alloy plated with a thin layer of passivated gold, while for THF0, the mesh will be made of niobium Nb, to avoid interferences from residual magnetic fields in the metal. The meshes have a blocking factor of about 2% that needs to be taken into consideration during the quantum efficiency calculations of the detectors.

3.2 The WFI optical blocking filters

The current WFI LDA and FD detectors design admits an OBF directly deposited onto the sensor chip(s) made of 90 nm Al / 30 nm Si₃N₄ / 20 nm SiO₂, and it was found that the optical transmission guaranteed by this OBF alone is, for most of the spectral band, at around 10⁻⁶, a value sufficient to reduce the UV/Vis flux to not affect the detector’s spectroscopic analysis of most high energy sources. Such an on-chip filter is, however, not sufficient to block the UV-Vis emission from a few bright sources including hot O-B type stars. Therefore, an additional OBF mounted on a FW is included in the WFI design to fully accomplish the science objectives of the mission related to young stars and stellar winds, as described in section 1. Moreover, another important requirement for the filters is the **ability to sustain**

vibro-acoustic loads during the launch: the design incorporates meshes and frames for structural stability, and the successful experiments discussed in Polak et al.[15] provided the evidence for the WFI filters to be able to sustain a launch at atmospheric pressure in the Ariane 6 heavy-lift space launch vehicle.

The detector's filter set consists of one OBF for the LDA and two OBFs (thin and thick) for the FD to be positioned in a FW. The nominal thicknesses of the LDA OBF and thin FD OBF, according to the UV-Vis rejection needs, is chosen to be PI – 150/Al – 30, and similarly to the filters for the other detector, these OBFs are also supported by Au plated BeCu meshes. Furthermore, the thick FD OBF needed to observe very bright X-ray sources consists of a mesh-less PI film 25 μm thick coated with 50 nm of aluminium on both sides. The design of the LDA OBF, as well as a picture of a representative breadboard, is found in figure 11.

Figure 11: On the left, the mounting scheme of the LDA OBF, with its four parts glued together: 1) inner frame, 2) outer frame, 3) mesh, 4) PI/Al film. On the right, a picture of a representative breadboard of the WFI LDA OBF mounted on a FW mock-up during the successful acoustic tests performed at AGH University in Krakow in July 2019, taken from the gallery WFI section of the Athena community website [2].

More information on the FW development can be found in [14, 17, 21].

4 An outline of filters in X-ray space astronomy

This section is more on the historic side of physics, and it will describe some of the most important steps that had thin filters involved in X-ray space missions, with particular attention to which filters and materials were employed, to the root causes for their employment, the functionality that they guaranteed, also detailing in the process some of the most important missions in X-ray astronomy. Much inspiration is taken from researchers deeply involved in

the study of thin filters in X-ray missions, and a rich reference is to be published soon in a work by M. Barbera, U. Lo Cicero and L. Sciortino [22], with far more details than addressed in this summary.

X-ray astronomy was born after the end of World War II in the 1950s and 1960s with the work of B. Rossi, G. Vaiana and R. Giacconi that resulted in the first major experiments dedicated to the sky observation in this electromagnetic spectral band. Furthermore, Giacconi was awarded the Nobel prize in physics in 2002 for ‘pioneering contributions to astrophysics, which led to the discovery of cosmic X-ray sources’ including his first-hand involvement in the Uhuru and Einstein X-ray missions [23, 24]. Since 1970 many satellites were sent out to space to detect and image X-ray sources, with most of them employing a way to focus X-ray beams towards a focal plane (i.e. a focusing set of mirrors) and all of them using a type of X-ray detector, with the likes of gas proportional counters (PC), microchannel plates (MCP), detectors based on semiconductors (CCD cameras), and, very recently, also microcalorimeters.

These instruments for various reasons, either related to the lower energies response or to the structure of the detectors themselves, require thin filters to augment their efficiency and for optimal decoding of X-ray signals. Resembling most of what was said in sections 3.1 and 3.2 for the case of Athena, the **main rationales** for OBFs / THFs employment in X-ray missions, either as mounted on a FW and used when necessary or in a fixed position in the beam path of the X-rays from the telescope, are summarised: they diminish the number of ultraviolet, visible and infrared photons arriving at the detector, which could cause problems in calibration, out-number the X-ray flux in power or increase the PSN; for the detectors with insufficient counting rate dynamic range, *ad hoc* filters with flat transmission percentages can be used to attenuate very bright sources and allow their detection; they can be used to select a band of the EM spectrum, as when coupled with spectrometers on board; by attenuating IR radiation, they improve the efficiency of cooling cryogenic systems; they shield the instrumentation from particle contamination due to either the out-gassing of the spacecraft’s surfaces or low energy cosmic charged particles; and, finally, metallised filters behave like a Faraday cages, thus shielding the detectors from surrounding EMIs generated by communication systems and/or on-board electronics, *en passant* reducing surface charging. It is also assumed that the filters are developed to endure as long as the mission requires, and clearly to also survive the launch.

Of secondary importance, the trade names of notorious **plastic materials** for X-ray astrophysical applications are described. Generally, polypropylene (C₃H₆) or Mylar / polyethylene

terephthalate ($C_{10}H_8O_4$) were some of the structural materials of choice for membrane support in the very first X-ray space missions. In addition, from the 1970s onward one of the main materials used in MTFs for X-ray missions was the polycarbonate commercially known as Lexan ($C_{16}H_{14}O_{13}$) [25]. This was used in EXOSAT, ROSAT and other missions mainly for its UV attenuation properties. An alternative emerged in polyimide (PI, $C_{22}H_{10}N_2O_4$) available commercially in thin films and made by the Luxel Corporation. It was shown to be mechanically more robust as a filter structural layer for the acoustic loads of launches, and offered better UV blocking than polycarbonate, also maintaining a high X-ray transmission [26, 27]. Ever since their proposition, polyimide films were employed and, as will be assessed, they are still used in many X-ray missions, testifying to their scientific reliability.

Not all of the X-ray missions filters designs will be covered, but a few that are important to the cause of Athena: one of the first X-ray observatories ever conceived, EINSTEIN; two of the most important ones even today, XMM-Newton and Chandra; and, at last, Hitomi, described as a modern example of an observatory with a microcalorimeter. Only slight references will be dedicated to other important missions.

The NASA **Einstein** [28], launched into low-Earth orbit in 1978, was the first satellite to use a focusing X-ray telescope and multiple detectors with X-ray imaging capabilities, and it was operative until 1981. Its main instruments were the Imaging Proportional Counter (IPC) and the High Resolution Imager (HRI). The IPC was a gas-filled position-sensitive imaging proportional counter, and its two modules employed different types of *leak-tight* films at the entrance window: module A employed a MTF made of polypropylene–2 μm /Lexan–0.4 μm , while module B used a mono-layer, Mylar – 3 μm . Both windows were coated with 0.2 μm of carbon to provide electrical conductivity. This first prosperous observatory laid the basis for the following X-ray observatories: Wolter I optics, multiple detectors at the focal plane, the employment of micrometric filters, and lastly, the possibility to allocate observing time to global guest observers, all feats shared also with the Athena project.

A few important missions followed: EXOSAT (1983-1986), ROSAT (1990-1999), Asuka (1993-2000). A particular mention is given to the Italian-Dutch program BeppoSAX (1996-2003) [29], one of the first missions to employ thin film filters with polyimide successfully. These were the ancestors of the following ‘current generation’ great X-ray observatories.

The first of which is NASA’s **Chandra** observatory [30]. Launched into near-Earth orbit in 1999, it is still functional. Its payload, designed for imaging and spectroscopy in the X band, is made of Wolter I grazing incidence X-ray optics with high angular resolution (0.5'' FWHM) and four selectable focal plane detectors: the Advanced CCD Imaging Spectrometer

(ACIS), with its two parts, ACIS-I, a 2×2 array of 4 CCD chips, and ACIS-S, a linear array of 6 CCD chips for high-energy spectroscopy in the range 0.4 – 10 keV; and the High Resolution Camera (HRC) with two microchannel plates detectors, the HRC-I and the soft X-ray spectrometer HRC-S (with a range of 0.07 – 0.15 keV). As for the filters and similarly to Athena, PI/Al nanometric MTFs are employed. The ACIS detectors are protected by an OBF placed 2 cm above the detectors, with ACIS-I using a PI – 200 nm/Al – 160 nm MTF, while ACIS-S used a similar one with less aluminium, PI – 200 nm/Al – 130 nm. The HRC utilised similar MTFs, called UV/Ion shields, only a few mm's near the detector, being: for the HRC-I, PI \sim 550 nm/Al – 76 nm, and for the HRC-s, a filter with thinner polyimide was used, PI \sim 250 nm/Al \sim 50 nm. These filter configurations proved successful in avoiding UV-contamination of the data [31], but a loss of sensitivity at low energies was detected instead after the first years of the mission for the ACIS CCD detectors, later linked to molecular contamination layers [32]. The main speciality of Chandra is the high energy resolution X-ray spectroscopy at high angular resolutions done with HRC, and these aspects would be covered mostly by Athena's X-IFU detector, sharing with it also the same MTF materials. Chandra is a huge milestone for X-ray science and continues to be as of today a reference for all of the missions on development.

As important is the European X-ray Multi-Mirror Mission **XMM-Newton** [33], launched in near-Earth orbit in 1999 and, like Chandra, still in function, whose purpose is X-ray imaging and spectroscopy. Its payload consists of three co-aligned high effective area Wolter I X-ray telescopes, each having a CCD at the focal plane: one being a pn-CCD focused on spectral imaging, the other two being reflection grating spectrometers (RGS) with metal-oxide semiconductor (MOS) CCDs. These are collectively known as the European Photon Imaging Camera (EPIC). A mounted FW has three different MTFs to be chosen for the UV/vis attenuation: the thin PI – 160 nm/Al – 40 nm, the medium PI – 160 nm/Al – 80 nm and the thick Al – 100 nm/polypropylene – 300 nm/Al – 100 nm/Sn – 25 nm. The RGS MOS CCDs were equipped with on-chip OBFs consisting of thin aluminium layers (\sim 45 – 75 nm thick) isolated from the silicon substrate by a MgF_2 \sim 26 nm thick layer. Oppositely to Chandra, XMM-Newton did not show the same molecular contamination levels after the first years of the mission [34], but, from 2013 onward, contamination modelled as pure carbon deposited on the MOS CCD cameras was detected [35], although there is no evidence of contamination on the pn-CCD yet. This great observatory still yields the astronomical community with great spectroscopy and imaging of the high energy space, and Athena's WFI would be its proper successor, improving on its characteristics.

Other missions pertaining to X-rays followed: Swift (2004-), also employing PI/Al filters, and Suzaku (2005-2015), a first attempt to use microcalorimeters, although the liquid cryostat maintaining the microcalorimeter cool failed after 29 days.

Suzaku's follower **Hitomi** [36] was a Japanese mission launched in 2016 in low Earth orbit. It went operational on February 17 and unfortunately lost communication with the ground on March 26, working for a total of a month and ten days. With a Wolter Type-1 optical system, it carried on the focal plane a Soft X-ray spectrometer (SXS) based on a microcalorimeter array with doped silicon sensors, providing the astronomical community with a further attempt at doing very high resolution X-ray spectroscopy. The filters used to shield this detector were three outer filters and two inner OBFs: the outer ones were made of PI – 100 nm/Al – 100 nm supported by the related mesh, while the inner OBFs were instead made of PI – 75 nm/Al – 50 nm. Although the mission was not long-lived, the scientific apparatus satisfied all of the requirements during the months' worth of working time, positively preparing the grounds for future observatories such as XRISM (to be launched in 2022) and Athena, both hosting a microcalorimeter respectively in Resolve and X-IFU.

Trying to sum up the heritage of the thin filters applications in X-ray science described above, figure 12 depicts the Tycho supernova remnant (SN 1572), whose J2000 coordinates are declination $+64^{\circ} 09'$ and right ascension $0^{\text{h}} 25.3^{\text{m}}$, respectively obtained from the data observed in some of the missions mentioned above, opportunely rendered in images transcribing X-ray fluxes into different colour intensities. These pictures are not fully representative of the capabilities of the missions involved, but can suggest some clues on the technological advancement ever occurring in modern (and future) X-ray astrophysics.

Figure 12: Three depictions of the Tycho SNR taken from different observatories. (a) An Einstein/HRI image. Credit: NASA/HEASARC. (b) An image obtained from X-ray light of the Chandra/ACIS. Credit: NASA / CXC / RIKEN & GSFC / T. Sato et al [37]. (c) An XMM-Newton / EPIC MOS image in the Fe-*XVII* line range (775, 855) eV silicon deconvolved. Credit: Decourchelle et al. [38].

Part II

Experimental setup and measurements

This part marks the beginning of the experimental core of this thesis, where the investigated aluminium and polyimide filter samples are described alongside the instruments used for the transmission analyses.

The ensuing transmission measurements were conducted in the EM-spectral range 190 – 25000 nm from ultraviolet to mid-infrared, utilising two different spectrometers: a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050+ was employed in the UV/Vis-IR range 190 ÷ 3000 nm, and a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR Spectrum 3 was used in the IR-MIR range 1500 ÷ 25000 nm, providing some overlap with the first instrument. These instruments and their optical systems will be detailed in the following sections, 5.1 and 5.2, along with the main experimental setup parameters of measurements.

The characteristics of the investigated filter samples and their transmission measurements obtained with the above instruments are reported in sections 6 and 7. The exact measurement parameters for each of the experimental data sets used are, instead, detailed in appendix A .

5 Experimental setup

5.1 Perkin-Elmer Spectrum-3

The MIR and FIR transmission measures were performed with the Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 3™ FT-IR instrument, based on the technique of Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. Figure 13 provides pictures of the instrument with the sample compartment closed (left) or open (right).

It is customary in IR spectroscopy to describe the spectral band with *wavenumbers* instead of *wavelengths* or *energy*, more widespread for general use. Since many times in the work the units for electromagnetic wavenumbers $\tilde{\nu}$ [cm^{-1}], wavelengths λ [nm] or energy E [eV] will be used interchangeably, their conversion factors are hereby listed for ease of reference².

$$\tilde{\nu}[\text{cm}^{-1}] = \frac{10^7}{\lambda[\text{nm}]}, \quad \tilde{\nu}[\text{cm}^{-1}] = 1.239842 \times 10^{-4} E [\text{eV}], \quad \lambda[\text{nm}] = \frac{1239.842}{E [\text{eV}]} \quad (1)$$

The Spectrum 3 optical system consists of a sealed and desiccated interferometer-optical unit along with a vibration isolated baseplate on which the samples are mounted. A rotary

²1.239842 are the significant digits in hc [eV nm], Planck's constant times the speed of light in a vacuum

Figure 13: The Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 3 FT-IR instrument. On the left, is the general appearance of the instrument. On the right, is a view of the instrument when the sample compartment lid is open.

Michelson interferometer, self-compensating for dynamic alignment changes, is employed for scanning, patented by Perkin Elmer™. As for the source, it is a hot MIR lamp (Mini-Igniter™ Model 301), emitting in the range $8000 - 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (i.e. $1250 - 333000 \text{ nm}$). Its beamsplitter is made of standard optimised potassium bromide KBr working in the range $7800 - 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the detector is a MIR thermal pyroelectric radiation detector composed of Deuterated Lanthanum Alanine doped TriGlycine Sulphate (DLTGS) working in the range $15000 - 370 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The instruments allow for user customisation, hence the following specifications are generally related to our experiments. Usually, for sample measurements, the scanning was performed in the range $7800 - 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a scan speed (SS) of 0.2 cm s^{-1} , the resolution was fixed at 4 cm^{-1} , the data interval was 0.4 cm^{-1} , and the number of scans accumulation was set at 128: this set of parameters was found to be a good compromise to obtain a peak signal-to-noise ratio of $S/N > 20000$.

FT-IR measurements in general have constant spectral resolution throughout the range in wavenumber. If wavenumbers are converted to wavelength with relation 1, the resolution, in general, varies as a function of wavelength. By equating the relative error of the two quantities we obtain:

$$\frac{\Delta\tilde{\nu}}{\tilde{\nu}} = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda} \iff \Delta\lambda = \lambda^2\Delta\tilde{\nu} \quad (2)$$

Taking a look at the two bounds of the range, a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} at $\tilde{\nu} = 7800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, that is $\lambda = 1282.05 \text{ nm}$, corresponds to a wavelength resolution $\Delta\lambda = 0.66 \text{ nm}$, on the contrary, the same resolution at $\tilde{\nu} = 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\lambda = 25000 \text{ nm}$) results in a wavelength resolution of $\Delta\lambda = 250 \text{ nm}$.

To position the filters, using a specific frame type named TF110 (Luxel standard, see

section 6), into the sample compartment of both instruments, a proper sample holder was manufactured in-house. Figure 14 shows a picture of the sample holder inside the instrument sample compartment. The positioning of the sample in the sample holder is regulated by maximising the beam portion across the filter. By using the measurement parameters described above, the beam spot is circular with a diameter of about 9 mm.

Figure 14: Lateral view of the sample holder in the sample compartment of Spectrum 3, holding a hollow (filter-less) Luxel TF110 frame. A rotating screw (upper-left of the picture) can be used to regulate the height of the sample with respect to the infrared beam coming from the source to the left, allowing for repeatable execution of measurements with spot-on beam centring. Taken at XACT.

To derive the sample transmission, two distinct measures are required: the background, performed with an empty TF110 frame positioned on the beam, and a second one with the filter sample in the beam position. Using the same TF110 frame ensures that the light beam is partialised equally in both measurements, minimising systematic errors. The formula for the transmission is described in the equation 8 in the following section.

The principles of FT-IR spectroscopy are now detailed to complete the introduction on the instrument and techniques employed to measure the filter transmission in the IR-MIR.

5.1.1 Principles of IR and FT-IR spectroscopy

It is impossible to cover in great detail everything that there is to know - or anything, really - about IR spectroscopy and the technique of FT-IR, but the most important aspects will be outlined in this section. Details about these topics and techniques can be found in technical book, like that by P. R. Griffiths [39], or in textbooks of general spectroscopy, as that of J. M. Hollas [40] where some of the following formulas are inspired from.

IR-spectroscopy, more frequently assessed as vibrational spectroscopy, involves the study

of the interaction of infrared light with matter in the range $10 - 14300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, usually divided in its three smaller sub-parts: the near-infrared or NIR, $14300 - 5000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; the mid-infrared or MIR, $5000 - 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and the far-infrared or FIR, $500 - 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ - where the definition of these boundaries may vary according to different authors. Infrared spectroscopy is a great probing technique for the motion of nuclei and works well in detecting vibrational bands for known chemical bonds, especially for organic compounds, as the energy of such photons are sufficient to excite the molecules absorbing them in vibrational and rotational frequencies. A comprehensive account of absorption spectra and vibrational modes of some of the most important chemical compounds can be found in Günzler et al. [41, Chap. 6.4], or in the book by Harris et al. [42, Chap. 3-11].

Although the usual IR-spectroscopy techniques involve the use of a monochromator in a similar fashion to what will be discussed for the UV/Vis spectrometer, the FT-IR is a procedure that does not require a monochromator, falling into the category of multiplexed techniques. In these, a polychromatic light beam source is used, which is split using a beam splitter, reflected by proper mirrors, resulting in the interference spectra of two signals that probe the sample and go towards the detector. A simplified optical system describing FT-IR spectrometers is shown in figure 15.

Figure 15: A simple FT-IR spectrometer employing an interferometer based on the original Michelson scheme [43] with a movable mirror. A polychromatic IR light is emitted by the source and sent to the beamsplitter. The signal is then partially transmitted to the mirrors. Both signals are reflected and then recombine, approaching first the sample - if there is one - and then the detector, being digitally processed.

Let us now describe in principle how the multi-wavelength signal can be de-constructed to yield the transmission at each spectral component, based on said picture. Let the spectral

intensity of the signal emitted at the source be $I_0(\omega)$ with its electric field $\mathbf{E}(\omega)$. In complex notation, the electric field of a monochromatic plane wave is described as follows:

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 \exp(i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)) \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{E}_0 is the (vector) amplitude of the signal, $\mathbf{k} = n\omega/c \mathbf{s}$ denotes the wave vector, \mathbf{r} the position vector, n the refractive index of the medium in which the wave propagates, ω the spectral frequency of the signal, c the speed of light and \mathbf{s} the direction of propagation of the signal. The signal is divided by the beam splitter in two parts, \mathbf{E}_1 and \mathbf{E}_2 , each of them with the same amplitude \mathbf{E}_0 : these signals will recombine at the detector after reflecting onto the mirrors. Calling d_1 the distance between the beam splitter and the fixed mirror, and d_2 the analogous distance with respect to the movable mirror, and defining $x = d_2 - d_1$, the optical path difference between the two signals (considering also the reflections) is $2kx$. The electric field (say, without the presence of the sample) at the detector would then be (using also $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ and a common phase $\phi(t)$ containing the time dependence):

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_1 + \mathbf{E}_2 = \mathbf{E}_0 \exp(i\phi(t)) \left(1 + \exp\left(i\frac{4\pi x}{\lambda}\right) \right) \quad (4)$$

The signal received at the detector is the intensity (measured in erg s^{-1}) which is proportional to the square of the real part of equation 4. By doing this mathematical calculation, using also the fact that $\langle \cos^2(\phi(t)) \rangle = 1/2$, one obtains the spectral intensity at the detector due to the interference of the apparatus:

$$I(\omega) = I_0(\omega) \left(1 + \cos\left(\frac{4\pi x}{\lambda}\right) \right) \quad (5)$$

Since no dispersive component is employed in the optical system, the detector reveals the total signal intensity, which is the integral of all the spectral components of eq. 5³, resulting in the often called *interferogram*. If the substitution $2\pi/\lambda = \omega/c$ is employed, this total signal intensity can mathematically be represented as a function of mirror displacement x .

$$S(x) = \int_0^{+\infty} I_0(\omega) \left(1 + \cos\left(\frac{2\omega x}{c}\right) \right) d\omega \quad (6)$$

By applying a (cosine-)Fourier transform to this signal - giving the technique its name - one can restore the original spectral intensity.

$$I_0(\omega) = \frac{2}{\pi c} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(S(x) - \frac{S(0)}{2} \right) \cos\left(\frac{2\omega x}{c}\right) d\omega \quad (7)$$

³A more thorough description of the interferogram, taking into account other realistic effects such as the non-ideality of the beamsplitter, is found in Griffiths [39, Chap. 2.2]

If a sample is inserted in-between the ray, introducing a transmission factor $T(\omega)$ in eq. 5 as $I_0(\omega) \mapsto I'(\omega) = T(\omega)I_0(\omega)$, the spectral intensity $I'(\omega)$ can be de-constructed in the manner described above for the signal without the sample. Then, having the interferograms in both cases, with and without the sample, the transmission simply follows, as the ratio between the spectral intensity transmitted through the sample, $I'(\omega)$, and the spectral intensity measured without sample, $I_0(\omega)$ (called *background* measure). The absorbance is also described in the following equation, being equivalent to the transmission measure, but on a logarithmic scale. Both A and T are non-dimensional quantities.

$$T(\omega) = \frac{I'(\omega)}{I_0(\omega)} \quad \text{and} \quad A(\omega) = -\log_{10}(T(\omega)) \quad (8)$$

The function $T(\omega)$ so obtained is the true observable of the process, and contains all of the available information about the sample (the information about the environment, or the lamp, is stored in the background spectrum).

The ability to resolve accurately the spectral intensity by the instrument relies much upon the ability to make accurate measurements of the interferogram, with a fine mirror displacement Δx and a large portion of the x -range. In general, the highest wavenumber the instrument is able to probe relates to the smallest step Δx the movable mirror can perform, whereas the resolution $\Delta\tilde{\nu}$ is instead related to the portion of the interferogram that is available for the Fourier transform, which, in turn, depends on the maximum displacement x_{\max} of the movable mirror. Both of these statements are summarised in the following approximate equations:

$$\tilde{\nu}_{\max} \approx (\Delta x)^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta\tilde{\nu} \approx (x_{\max})^{-1} \quad (9)$$

As an ending remark, as was first noted by P.B. Fellgett in his PhD thesis [44], multiplexed measurements such as those made by Fourier transform spectrometers satisfy the so-called *multiplex advantage*, also known as *Fellgett's advantage*, which consists of an improvement in signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of multiplexed techniques, with respect to those employing an equivalent system where a monochromator is employed for spectral resolving, in the cases where the dominant source of noise is the instrumental detector noise, although this advantage is offset when measurements are dominated by shot noise [39, pp.169-171].

5.2 Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050+

The UV-Vis and NIR transmission spectra were obtained via the Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050+, which is a more traditional double-beam spectrometer, although very ingenious since

various parts are automatised together to obtain a spectrum in these different spectral regions which require diverse optical components to be exchanged when needed. A visual overview of the instrument is shown in figure 16.

Figure 16: The Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050+ UV/Vis/NIR spectrophotometer. On the left, a general view of the instrument when closed. On the right, a view of the instrument when both the sample compartment (to the left) and the detectors compartment are open.

As previously mentioned, the instrument was employed for measurements in the range from 190 to ~ 2500 nm, covering the spectral bands of UV, visible and near-infrared. Here follows a general description of the measurement set-up, where in this case as well the instrument allows for user-customised measurement procedures: this is important because due to the diverse spectral bands, there are two interchangeable detectors, lamps, and monochromators, along with different settings. If the sample is too opaque, there are automatic internal attenuators available to be inserted individually into the sample beam and the reference beam - their usage, when needed, is specified in appendix A .

The instrument is equipped with: two lamps, a deuterium (D_2) lamp, for the range 190 – 319.20 nm and a tungsten-halogen lamp emitting in the range (319.20, 3300 nm); two detectors, a photomultiplier tube PMT for the ~ 190 – 860.60 nm range and a lead sulphide (PbS) detector working in the range ~ 860.60 – 3300 nm; and two monochromators switching by default at 860.60 nm. In the upper 860.60 – 3300 nm wavelength range, besides the above-mentioned source, detector and monochromator, the main components of the optical system are: a NIR slit with a width set on Servo mode; a common beam mask (CBM) usually set either at 50% or 30%; the attenuators, respectively for the sample beam and the reference beam. The lead sulphide detector works with a variable response set from 0.4 to 4.0 s, with a gain fixed at 1.0. In the lower range ~ 190 – 860.60 nm, the gain of the photomultiplier

tube (PMT) detector is set on Automatic, its response is set at 0.4 s, and correspondingly, the UV/Vis slit spectral width is set at 5 nm. At wavelengths lower than 319.20 nm, the deuterium (D_2) lamp becomes operational. The data interval is also specified, usually chosen as 1, 2 or 5 nm. The view of the data collection window as shown in the software while operating with the instrument, which summarises the typical parameters used and described above along with the optical system, is given in figure 17.

Figure 17: The Data Collection window as displayed in the UV WinLab software - the dedicated Perkin Elmer™ program for instrument control and data manipulation - while it is connected to the Lambda 1050+ instrument and before the start of a measure. All of the main data collection parameters are displayed, as well as a schematic view of the optical system.

The instrumental photometric accuracy, as described by the manufacturer, is of the order of 0.001 A (absorbances) and, additionally, the wavelength accuracy is of the order of 0.025 nm at 656.1 nm and 0.200 nm at 1312.7 nm. More details are available in the ‘Typical Specifications of the High-Performance Lambda 1050+ UV/Vis/NIR Spectrophotometer’ booklet [45].

To create both the reference and sample beams, a chopper assembly (resembling a rotating disk) alternates 4 optical components - a mirror segment, a window segment and two dark segments. When the window segment enters the beam, radiation passes through and creates

the sample beam. When the mirror segment enters the beam, the radiation is reflected and through a second set of mirrors forms the reference beam.

Three measures are required with the same parameters in order to output one sample transmission result. The first measure is done by the instrument without the sample, to measure the 100% T or 0 A *baseline*, which the instrument automatically employs to auto-zero the measurement. The second measure is the 0% T (*blocked beam baseline*). It is obtained using an internal attenuator and is used to correct for electronic and thermal detector noise. Finally, the third and final measurement is taken with the sample. To speed up the measures (which can take up to hours), a semi-automatic leverage system was designed by INAF-XACT engineers along with other manufacturers to automatically bring the sample in and out of the beam path during the baseline and sample transmission measurements.

As stated in the instrument manual the beam spot is not circular but supposedly rectangular, with a width of $4 \div 5$ mm, varying with the spectral slit width, and a maximum height of $11.7 - 0$ mm, depending on the % value of the CBM. Due to the non-cylindrical nature of the beam, and the fact that its height at CBM 100% exceeds the TF110 filter sample aperture, the CBM was always set at either 30% or 50% so that the beam cross-section would be entirely contained in the sample.

5.2.1 Principles of UV/Vis and NIR transmission spectroscopy

UV/Vis-NIR spectroscopy is an experimental technique that is used in many scientific cases. Hence only an outline will be given, with further details available in the aforementioned general spectroscopy books [40, 42].

In general, UV/Vis transmission spectroscopy involves the study of transitions in absorption between the electronic states of an atom or a molecule (or a more complex aggregate of molecules) as excitation light is shined onto them in the wavelength range between $\lambda \in (200, 1000)$ nm. At longer wavelengths, i.e. $(1000, 2000)$ nm, the spectroscopy falls yet again in the infrared or vibrational regime already described, whereas in the lower range $\lambda \in (10, 200)$ nm this is UV or Extreme-UV spectroscopy, which usually requires more care about the environment by employing vacuum technologies to be properly executed.

Its goal is to measure the transmittance of a sample or, equivalently, its absorbance. If I_λ^0 is the spectral intensity sent by a source with no sample in between the beam path, and I_λ is the same spectral intensity being transmitted through the sample under study, the transmission is given by their ratio - analogously to equation 8 - and the absorbance can again be described

via the use of the logarithm. The only difference, in this case, is that the spectral intensity is directly measured by actively resolving each wavelength through a monochromator, instead of indirectly calculating it from a mathematical procedure.

$$T(\lambda) = \frac{I_\lambda}{I_\lambda^0} \quad \text{and} \quad A(\lambda) = -\log_{10}(T(\lambda)) \quad (10)$$

The transmission is the true observable describing the sample, containing all of the information obtainable from this technique, such as the electronic transitions.

The absorption rate of a transition of a generic system is linked to its intrinsic properties, such as the dipole moment of the transition under study. Usual techniques to study electronic transmission spectra involve the employment of Einstein coefficients, fixed-line shapes, and the use of known physical laws such as Beer's law. This law does not generally hold for the study of very thin filters due to the multiple reflections and the Fabry-Perot-like interferences which can affect the overall transmission. Much attention will be later given to the correct transmission models, but a description of these general laws of spectroscopic interest is found in Hollas [40, Chap. 2].

A simple diagram of the double beam spectroscopy used by the Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050+ is laid out in figure 18, while greater details are available in the manual of the instrument.

Figure 18: Scheme of a double-beam optical absorption apparatus analogous to that of Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050+. A source emits white light that is selected by a monochromator and a tunable slit. The monochromatic beam interacts with a rotating disk (chopper assembly) which alternates between a hollow component, which forms the sample beam, two dark components, and a mirror component, which reflects the ray into the reference beam. The transmittance is computed as the ratio between the intensity of the transmitted beam and the intensity of the reference beam.

The resolution of the spectrophotometer is usually limited by the resolving power of the monochromator and the accuracy of the detector, and the optical system favours the use of mirrors rather than lenses to minimise chromatic aberrations.

In conclusion, UV/Vis and NIR spectrometers employ different components in order to perform well in all of the spectral bands. Since the MTFs to be analysed have either a very low absorbance (such as PI which is virtually transparent in infrared) or, in the case of the PI/Al samples, they are very opaque, these instruments are easily brought to the limits of their dynamical range.

The next section describes the filter samples investigated in this work, whereas section 7 reports the plots of the measured transmission data.

6 Filter samples under study

Two kinds of filters have been analysed, either mono-layer, with only free-standing polyimide, or bi-layers with free-standing polyimide and aluminium. All of the measured samples were manufactured by Luxel Corp. (Friday Harbor, Washington), and their ID number, materials and nominal thicknesses are listed in Table 2. The notation mimics the one used in section 3.1.

Table 2: List of the measured samples including the identification number given by the manufacturer, material, and nominal thicknesses of each layer (in nm). PI stands for polyimide ($C_{22}H_{10}N_2O_4$), Al for aluminium.

ID Number	Material(s)-Thickness(es)
TF110-2476	PI – 45
TF110-2482	PI – 150
TF110-2466	PI – 415
TF110-2475	PI – 45/Al – 20
TF110-2462	PI – 45/Al – 30
TF110-2460	PI – 150/Al – 30

The samples will be addressed either by the ID number or by their nominal composition and thickness in the following chapters (hence, PI – 45 will denote filter TF110-2476 and vice versa). Each filter is supported by an aluminium frame, dubbed ‘TF110’, which is seen in the ID number. This is a standard support frame used by Luxel Corp. whose specifications

can be found in the website <https://luxel.com/products/filters/filter-frames/> (last visited on 05/06/2022). The clear aperture diameter is 10.2 mm. A picture of all the filters used in the experimental analyses is shown in figure 19.

Figure 19: A collection of six pictures of the analysed filter samples inside their safety plastic boxes. The three aluminised filters are on the top row, while the three mono-layer samples are on the lower row, thinnest to thickest from right to left as can be derived from the reported "material-thickness" code below the ID number. The filter on the lower right (the PI – 45) usually forms a convex shape due to its very thin layer (the thinnest in the group).

The thin PI and PI/Al film production techniques are patented by Luxel. There are many production techniques in general for thin filters, such as evaporation or sputtering known as physical vapour deposition (PVD), chemical vapour deposition (CVD), electrospinning, atomic layer deposition (ALD), spin coating (SC), and so forth, and each of them has unique advantages and drawbacks in terms of the corresponding surface defects. For example, in PVD, the formation of isles during the nm-growth deposition might occur, and this can impact the lower limit of thickness reachable by the technique. Some details regarding thin film production techniques can be found in the related references by Frey et al. [46] and Macleod [47].

Very thin MTFFs with metal layers are known to naturally produce a very thin oxide layer when exposed to air, which in the case of aluminium is expected to be of ~ 3 nm at the interfaces between Al and other layers and/or on the air-exposed surface [48, 49]. Since the oxidation of aluminium naturally and thermally happens, it must be taken into consideration in the transmission modelling of part III. It is not yet clear whether measurements at synchrotron beamlines could augment the oxide layer thickness, but there is evidence that exposure to high solar fluxes in the case of the Russian TESIS solar observatory for 7 years resulted in a probable increase of the oxide thicknesses for the used metal-silicon MTFFs [50]. Moreover, it is unknown whether environmental changes (such as temperature and humidity seasonal cycles) could have an influence in the presence of surface defects, and contribute to the total thickness amount of oxide in the aluminium layer, especially for PI/Al filters. As a heuristic interpretation, it is a possibility since it is known that polyimide or plastic foils under the correct circumstances can absorb and exude water [51], and there may be effects of moisture-penetration patterns in metal oxides in thin films [47, pp. 581-582]. These aspects are outside the main purpose of the thesis and could be of interest in follow-up studies.

7 Experimental data

The measures, described in the following subsections for all of the investigated filter samples, were obtained by merging data taken with the two instruments, the Perkin-Elmer Lambda 1050+ (190 ÷ 2500 nm) and the Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 3 (2500 ÷ 25000 nm), described in section 5, available at the laboratories of the XACT facility of INAF-OAPA. The measures were performed between 2021 and 2022.

Transmission versus wavelength plots are reported in the full wavelength range, and some of the most important experimental feats are highlighted when necessary, for example when the change of monochromator is very evident, or other effects. These aspects would be highlighted either through insets in the graphs or via an entire new graph used for that purpose. Usually, the λ -axis is in logarithmic scale, and the T -axis in linear scale, although, for the more opaque samples, transmission graphs are shown in logarithmic scale to better show the dynamic range.

The first samples whose transmission will be described are the monolayer polyimide ones, TF110-2476, TF110-2482 and TF110-2466 followed by the aluminium-coated filter samples TF110-2475, TF110-2462 and TF110-2460, ordered by increasing thicknesses.

7.1 PI-45 (TF110-2476)

The PI – 45 sample is the thinnest of all six samples.

The experimental data were obtained in the range 190 – 2500 nm with the Lambda 1050+, and in the range 2500.25 – 25000 nm with Spectrum 3. Whenever necessary, since the plots are all given in transmission T versus wavelength λ [nm], the data was converted following the laws described in equations 1.

The MIR transmission was obtained as the average of three different measures made with the same sample, performing a random rotation of the filter frame with respect to the IR-beam axis between each measurement - this is the case for all the MIR measurements and will not be stressed any further. For these particular filters, the MIR measures showed variability of about $0.005 T$, although usually, the instrument's photometric accuracy is more precise than this variation, with an accuracy of around $0.001 T$ for transparent samples. This variability could be either related to the mechanical movement of the sample membrane or its surface non-homogeneity.

Figures 20 and 21, are respectively a full transmission plot of the sample (along with insets of the monochromator and instrument change effects on the plot) in the whole range and a more in-depth look at the MIR structure of the sample.

Overall, the sample is highly structured in the MIR range with many absorption bands and it is very transparent in the optical and infrared band, with $T > 60\%$ for $\lambda \geq 400$ nm, and becoming more absorbing in the ultraviolet range (190, 300) nm, although it must be noted that air O_2 content may compromise the exact transmission. The monochromator change at $\lambda = 860.60$ nm affects the measure with a jump of $\approx 0.011 T$ whereas the instrument change occurring at 2500 nm is less noticeable, with a downward jump of $\approx 0.005 T$.

The many visible absorption lines found for this and the subsequent thicker PI samples are characteristic of polyimide films and they were found in the existing literature in experimental works such as those by Zhang et al. [52] and by Dhakshnamoorthy et al. [53]. The latter study in particular identified the presence of chemical bonds such as C=O and C–N, compatible with the polyimide monomer structure $C_{22}H_{10}N_2O_4$. A more detailed discussion will be provided in the modelling results section 9.3.

Figure 20: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2476, nominal thickness 45 nm, in the range (190, 25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles, and in the graph, two insets showcase the effect of the change of monochromator and of the instrument.

Figure 21: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2476, nominal thickness 45 nm, in the MIR range (5000, 25000) nm. This plot depicts the very complex IR structure of polyimide in the range.

7.2 PI-150 (TF110-2482)

The PI – 150 sample is the second thinnest of the monolayer samples. The experimental conditions and parameters of measurement are the same as for the PI-45. The MIR transmission was obtained as the average of three different measures with the same characteristics, obtained by applying a small rotation of the sample with respect to the beam: in this case, the variability of these measures was well within the instrument's standards. Figures 22 and 23, are respectively a full transmission plot of the sample in the whole range, along with insets closely monitoring the monochromator change and the UV band, and a more in-depth look at the MIR structure of the sample. The instrument change at $\lambda = 2500$ nm causes a jump of the order of $\sim 6 \times 10^{-4} T$, which is less significant than in the case of sample PI-45.

Overall, similarly to the case of PI-45, the PI-150 sample is highly structured in the MIR range and is also very transparent in the optical and infrared band, although an increase of about $\times 3$ in thickness causes the absorption bands to be slightly deeper for this sample (in accordance with Beer's law). Generally, the transmission is very transparent too in the optical range and infrared range, satisfying $T > 60\%$ for $\lambda \geq 400$ nm, but a major difference is that now the sample is much more opaque in the UV range, with $T < 6.5 \times 10^{-3}$ for $\lambda \in (190, 250)$ nm. An influence of thickness can be seen in the *interference bands* or *patterns* in figure 22, which will be part of the analysis and modelling sections: the first peak of interference bands is visible at $\lambda \simeq 596$ nm while the second peak is hidden by the complex MIR absorption bands.

Figure 22: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2482, nominal thickness 150 nm, in the range (190, 25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles, and in the graph, two insets showcase the effect of the change of the monochromator and of the very opaque UV portion.

Figure 23: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2482, nominal thickness 150 nm, in the MIR range (5000, 25000) nm. This plot depicts the very complex IR structure of polyimide in the range.

7.3 PI-415 (TF110-2466)

The PI – 415 sample is the thickest sample analysed in this work.

In the range 190–1492 nm the measure was employed with the Lambda 1050+ instrument, whereas in the complementary range 1492.09 – 25000 nm it was done with Spectrum 3. Figures 24 and 25 are respectively a full transmission plot of the sample in the whole range and a more in-depth look at the MIR structure of the sample. Since the transmission is very low at wavelengths in the ultraviolet, an inset in the logarithmic scale is showed in the total transmission graph. In this case, none of the instrument and monochromator change-related jumps is visible.

Overall, this sample too is transparent in the optical band and highly structured in the infrared one. Although $T \simeq 40\%$ is attained at some very strong absorption bands in the MIR range, it is generally satisfied that $T \gtrsim 70\%$ for $\lambda \geq 500$ nm, and the sample is extremely opaque in the UV range, reaching transmissions of $T \lesssim 4 \times 10^{-6}$ for $\lambda \in (200, 250)$ nm. In order to correctly measure the very low transmittance values ($T \sim 10^{-5.5} \div 10^{-6}$), the correct use of the reference beam attenuator is mandatory, and also these regions compete as well with the instrument stray light (which is of the order $A \sim 6 \Leftrightarrow T \sim 10^{-6}$, as specified by the instrument specifications furnished by the manufacturer). As a consequence, the measurement in the UV is also expected to be noisy. Most importantly, the interference bands are very visible in figure 24, with four visible peaks and valleys. As will be said, the manifestation of interference patterns - similar in the resulting transmitted intensity to what happens in a Michelson or Fabry-Perot interferometer - is a prominent feature of thin filters when studied at variable thicknesses, being mostly visible when the sample is not very absorptive. These aspects will be covered in part III.

Figure 24: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2482, nominal thickness 415 nm, in the range (190, 25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles. The inset shows the transmission in the UV range (190, 400) nm in logarithmic scale.

Figure 25: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2466, nominal thickness 415 nm, in the MIR range (5000, 25000) nm. This plot depicts the very complex IR structure of polyimide in the range.

7.4 PI-45/Al-20 (TF110-2475)

The first aluminium-coated sample to be characterised is the PI – 45/Al – 20. In the range 190 – 3140 nm the measure was done with the Lambda 1050+, and in the remaining range 3140.31 – 25000 nm it was collected with Spectrum 3.

Figures 26 and 27 are respectively full linear and logarithmic transmission plots of the sample in the whole range. The logarithmic scale plot is necessary since the sample reaches transmission of the order of $T \sim 10^{-2}$ that are not distinguishable in the simple linear transmission plot.

Overall, this sample is more opaque than the polyimide samples in all of the spectral region, transmitting at most $T \approx 17\%$. An important aspect is the low IR transmission measurement: for $\lambda \geq 2500$ nm, T is of the order of $10^{-2} \div 10^{-3}$. Although not evident in the transmission plot, because it appears to fall off very quickly in the infrared, it is plain that some instrumental noise affects the measure at the higher end of the range, particularly at about $\lambda = 20000$ (as shown in the inset of figure 27) where the signal-to-noise ratio drops significantly.

Figure 26: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2462, PI – 45/Al – 20, in the range (190,25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles. The inset shows the effect of the monochromator change around $\lambda \sim 860.6$ nm, causing a jump of $\sim 0.02 T$.

Figure 27: Measured transmission (in logarithmic scale) for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2462, PI – 45/Al – 20, in the range (190,25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles. The inset shows a rise in noise levels in the range (15000,25000) nm

7.5 PI-45/Al-30 (TF110-2462)

The second aluminised sample to be characterised is the PI-45/Al-30, which is currently the baseline for the THFs of the X-IFU instrument on Athena (section 3.1).

The measure was done with the Lambda 1050+ in the range 190 – 3225 nm and with Spectrum 3 in the range 3225.39 – 25000 nm. Figures 28 and 29 are respectively a linear transmission plot and a logarithmic one of the sample in the whole range.

Overall, this sample is more opaque than the previous samples in all of the region, transmitting at most 5%. An important aspect is the very low IR T -measurement: for $\lambda \geq 2500$ nm, the transmission is of the order of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \div 3 \times 10^{-4}$. The change of instrument lowers the noise affecting the data at $\lambda = 3225$ nm, from the NIR range of the Lambda 1050+ where the noise is of the order of $\Delta T \sim 10^{-3}$, to the NIR range of the Spectrum 3 where noise is two orders of magnitudes below ($\Delta T \sim 10^{-5}$). It is seen that instrumental noise affects the measure at the higher end of the range in the logarithmic-scale plot, particularly at about $\lambda = 20000$ as shown in the inset of figure 29, where there is a sharp rise in the signal-to-noise ratio.

Figure 28: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2462, PI – 45/Al – 20, in the range (190, 25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles. The inset shows the effect of the instrument change at around 3225 nm, lowering the noise.

Figure 29: Measured transmission in logarithmic scale for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2462, PI – 45/Al – 30, in the range (190, 25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles. The inset shows a rise in noise levels in the range (15000, 25000) nm.

7.6 PI-150/Al-30 (TF110-2460)

The third and last metallised sample to be characterised is the PI–150/Al–30, the thickest in the group and currently part of the baseline for the OBFs of the WFI instrument on Athena (sec. 3.2).

In the range 190 – 2500 nm the measure was done with the Lambda 1050+ instrument, whereas in the final range 2500.25 – 25000 nm the measure was performed with Spectrum 3.

Figures 30 and 31 are respectively a full transmission plot and a full absorbance plot of the sample in the whole range. The absorbance plot is necessary since the sample reaches transmission of the order of $T \sim 10^{-4}$ that are not distinguishable in the simple linear transmission plot.

Overall, this is the most absorbing and reflecting of the group of samples, transmitting at most 1.5%. An important aspect is the very low IR T -measurement: for $\lambda \geq 2500$ nm, the transmission is of the order of $10^{-3} \div 10^{-4}$. The change of instrument lowers the noise affecting the data at $\lambda = 2500.25$ nm, from the NIR range of the Lambda 1050+ where the noise is of the order of $\Delta T \sim 10^{-4}$ to the NIR range of the Spectrum 3 where noise is two orders of magnitudes below ($\Delta T \sim 10^{-6}$). The transmittance in the UV part of the region is also very high, of the order of $10^{-4} \div 3 \times 10^{-5}$ for $\lambda \leq 2500$ nm. It can be seen that instrumental noise significantly affects the measure at the higher end of the range in the logarithmic scale plot, particularly at about $\lambda = 20000$ as shown in the inset of figure 31, where the signal-to-noise ratio decreases dramatically.

This marks the conclusion of filter samples' characterisation, and the experimental data presentation.

Figure 30: Measured transmission for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2462, PI – 150/Al – 20, in the range (190, 25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles. The inset shows the effect of the instrument change at around 2500.25 nm, causing a jump in transmission and a change in noise levels.

Figure 31: Measured transmittance in logarithmic scale for the monolayer polyimide sample TF110-2462, PI – 150/Al – 30, in the range (190, 25000) nm. The data is represented by black circles. The inset shows a rise in noise level in the range (15000, 25000) nm.

Part III

Models, data analysis and discussion

This final part of the thesis is dedicated to discussing models and computational approaches used to derive the transmission of MTFs' based on PI and aluminium. The main goals of this part are the following:

- Introduce the concepts of complex refractive index (n, κ) , the Forouhi Bloomer models for these indexes, and the Transfer-Matrix Method employed to calculate the transmission of multilayer (ML) filters;
- Review the available data of (n, κ) for both Al and thin film / amorphous Al_2O_3 , used in the subsequent analyses;
- Develop a protocol to retrieve the optical constants (n, κ) of polyimide-based on the measured data of the monolayer PI-samples and produce the Forouhi-Bloomer model in the form of coefficient tables;
- Describe quantitatively the thickness best fit values and associated statistical errors of each of the sample layers (polyimide PI, aluminium Al, and oxidised layers Al_2O_3), with particular attention to the Al-oxide content, also describing eventual shortcomings of the models;
- Give a visual display of the fit-model vs data in explanatory graphs;
- Summarise the findings and hint at possible follow-ups.

A schematic view of the employed Python script is given in appendix B and some further description of the algorithm is given in appendix C.

8 Modelling of multilayer thin film filters transmission

8.1 Introduction to the complex refractive index

The concept of complex refractive index is highly effective in describing the interaction of electromagnetic light with matter. A full description of the derivation of the most important formulas hereby described can be found in the milestone book "Principles of Optics" written by Born and Wolf [54], while a summarised version of the proof hereby follows.

As with many theories, it all starts with the basis of optics, that is the set of Maxwell equations. Here they are recalled, written in the *Gaussian* units - differences between these and their *SI* equivalent representations are detailed in the classics by Griffiths [55, Appendix C] or Jackson [56, Appendix 4].

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = 4\pi\rho \quad (11)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{j} + \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} \quad (12)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (13)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Where \mathbf{D} is the *electric displacement*, \mathbf{H} the *magnetic vector*, \mathbf{E} the *electric vector*, and \mathbf{B} the *magnetic induction*, while \mathbf{j} is the free *electric current density* and ρ the free *electric charge density*. In a linear and isotropic medium, these quantities are linked together by some specific constants as follows.

$$\mathbf{j} = \sigma \mathbf{E} \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \varepsilon \mathbf{E} \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mu \mathbf{H} \quad (17)$$

Where the medium is characterised by the constants σ , the *specific conductivity*, ε , the *dielectric constant*, and μ , the *magnetic permeability*.

It can be proven that in complete absence of sources - *i. e.* $\mathbf{j} = 0$ and $\rho = 0$ - the field made of electric and magnetic vectors, (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{H}) , satisfies an important differential equation related to the medium (the same differential equation applies to both vectors separately).

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{\varepsilon\mu}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{H}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (18)$$

A general wave-plane solution for the electric field has the form - in complex notation, as described in eq. 3, repeated to ensure clarity:

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 \exp(i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \delta - \omega t)) \quad (19)$$

Where the wave vector \mathbf{k} has a precise unit direction \mathbf{s} and module $\|\mathbf{k}\| = k$, which formally satisfies, by substitution of this definition back into equation 18:

$$k^2 = \frac{\omega^2 \mu \varepsilon}{c^2} \quad (20)$$

If a more complete approach was taken, employing $\mathbf{j} = \sigma \mathbf{E}$ as an additional source term in the Maxwell equations, the wave equation would have a different form [54, p. 736] as follows:

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{\varepsilon \mu}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{H}) = \frac{4\pi \mu \sigma}{c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{H}) \quad (21)$$

And substituting in this differential equation the plane-wave solution 19 results in a different meaning to the wave vector norm squared:

$$k^2 = \frac{\omega^2 \mu}{c^2} \left(\varepsilon + i \frac{4\pi \sigma}{\omega} \right) \quad (22)$$

Therefore, a traditional approach is to define a complex dielectric function $\hat{\varepsilon} = \varepsilon_1 + i\varepsilon_2$ so that the equation above becomes effectively equivalent to $k^2 = \omega^2 \mu \hat{\varepsilon} / c^2$. Then, by defining k as $k = \hat{N} \omega / c$ one obtains the following equivalence:

$$\hat{N}^2 = \mu \hat{\varepsilon} \quad (23)$$

The quantity \hat{N} is the *complex refractive index*, and its components are generally defined as such: $\hat{N} = n + i\kappa$, where n is the *refractive index* and κ is the *extinction coefficient*. These components are related to those of the complex dielectric function - either by assuming $\mu \simeq 1$ or by incorporating μ into $\hat{\varepsilon}$ - as follows:

$$\varepsilon_1 = n^2 - \kappa^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon_2 = 2n\kappa \quad (24)$$

The reason κ is called *extinction coefficient* is that it is directly connected to the attenuation of the electric fields during transmission in a medium. If the wave vector \mathbf{k} was in the direction \hat{z} , substituting $k = \hat{N} \omega / c$ in the general plane wave solution would result in eq. 19, described hereunder:

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\kappa \omega z}{c}\right) \exp\left(i\left(\frac{n \omega z}{c} - \delta - \omega t\right)\right) \quad (25)$$

This in turn means that the electromagnetic field *intensity*, proportional to the square of the electric field amplitude, satisfies:

$$I = I_0 \exp\left(-\frac{2\kappa \omega z}{c}\right) \quad (26)$$

The notion of complex refractive index naturally extends the validity of the plane-wave electromagnetic solutions inside absorbing media, and it also connects well with the quantum mechanics treatment of light absorption, as this can be incorporated inside the κ .

There are other quantities used for describing materials' absorption characteristics, equivalent in principle to the extinction coefficient. One of them is the *absorption coefficient* α [cm^{-1}] defined as $\alpha = 2\kappa\omega/c$, whilst another is the *absorption cross-section* σ [cm^2], defined as α/n_d where n_d is the density of absorbers in the medium. Generally speaking, κ and σ do not depend on the density of absorbers in the medium, and all of the functions defined up to here are also function of the electromagnetic pulsation frequency ω , and a general relation of the form of $n(\omega)$ and $\kappa(\omega)$ is a *dispersion* equation.

Due to its importance in describing the optical properties of materials, many models were developed in the last century to describe the complex refractive index of a large class of materials. However, it has to be stressed that there is no possible way of measuring directly n and κ of a material. Experimental data for (n, κ) can be measured indirectly, being retrieved from, for example, ellipsometry, reflectance and/or transmittance measurements [57], hence the need of models is also a means to facilitate the extraction of these parameters. One famous model is the *Lorentzian* one, which emerges from the exact solution of the elementary electron theory of the motion of a charged damped harmonic oscillator under the influence of an electric field. The exact solution, under the approximation of $n \sim 1$ and in the case where there are multiple oscillators with different resonant frequencies, has the form [58, Chap. 31-3], for the (n, κ) pair:

$$n(\omega) = 1 + \sum_j \left(\frac{A_j (\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2 \omega^2} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa(\omega) = \sum_j \left(\frac{A_j \gamma_j \omega}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2 \omega^2} \right) \quad (27)$$

Where each j -th absorption band is characterised by the triplet $(\omega_j, A_j, \gamma_j)$ related to, respectively, its centre of absorption, its peak, and the FWHM of the profile. A plot is given, representative of the appearance of one Lorentzian absorption band, in figure 32.

As a matter of fact, n and κ , although different in shape, are not independent and they are related by the *Kramers-Kronig* relations, named after the physicists who first discovered them [59, 60]. These relations naturally emerge as a consequence of causality in the connection $\mathbf{D}(\omega) = \varepsilon(\omega) \mathbf{E}(\omega)$ between \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{E} , if mathematically investigated via Fourier superposition to extract the time dependence $\mathbf{E}(t)$ as shown in the reference by Jackson [56, Chap. 7.10]. The integral relations are described in the equations below, where \mathcal{P} denotes the Cauchy principal value.

$$\begin{cases} n(\omega) = +\frac{1}{\pi} \mathcal{P} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\kappa(\nu)}{\nu - \omega} d\nu = +\frac{2}{\pi} \mathcal{P} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\nu}{\nu^2 - \omega^2} \kappa(\nu) d\nu \\ \kappa(\omega) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \mathcal{P} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{n(\nu)}{\nu - \omega} d\nu = -\frac{2}{\pi} \mathcal{P} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\omega}{\nu^2 - \omega^2} n(\nu) d\nu \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Figure 32: Plot of the typical appearance of a Lorentzian model as in eq. 27, in both the real n and imaginary κ parts of the complex refractive index, where only one absorption band is represented with components $(\omega_0, A, \gamma) = (3, 1, 0.3)$. Qualitatively, the shape is a common sight in (n, κ) data with absorption bands.

These integral equations, which are detailed in the book by Arfken and Weber [61, Chap. 7.2], relate the real and imaginary part of a function - in this case $\hat{N}(\omega)$ - and they are known in the literature as *Hilbert transforms*, or *dispersion relations*. The same set of integral equations is satisfied not only by the complex refractive index and its components (n, κ) , but also by the complex dielectric function⁴, and the relative components $(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2)$.

Of the many successful dispersion models employed for materials in general, and thin films in particular, some of the most prolific and used - either as initially presented or with some variations - are: for amorphous materials, insulators and semiconductors, Forouhi-Bloomer's 1988 [63], Tauc-Lorentz [64], and Sellmeier models [65, 66], but also commonly employed are the aforementioned Lorentz but also Gaussian profiles; mainly for metals, Drude-Lorentz models are mostly employed [67]. More recently in 2019 and 2021, Forouhi and Bloomer have published an update of their original models which will be discussed in details in the next section.

8.2 Forouhi-Bloomer 2019-2021 Models

The model published by Forouhi and Bloomer in 2019 is developed for amorphous, dielectric, insulating and polymer materials [68] while a second paper published in 2021 was

⁴Arfken and Weber also introduce the Titchmarsh theorem, which is a set of conditions for complex functions to satisfy the dispersion relations, and it is seen [62] that the conditions are satisfied by both \hat{N} and $\hat{\varepsilon}$.

dedicated to metals [69]. These articles, other than offering a substantiated review of the main models employed in materials characterisation, aim to improve their older models for both metal and dielectric materials. The model for metals is just briefly mentioned, whereas the model for dielectrics will be thoroughly introduced.

The 2019's article main aim is to describe non-metals or non-crystalline materials by a set of coefficients which would cover the complex refractive index in a given range of energies, in a fashion similar to how a limited number of Fourier's coefficients suffice to describe a complex periodic signal. As of today, there exists no unified way of describing the (n, κ) optical constants of materials, besides huge lists in dedicated textbooks or articles [57, 70], hinting at the need for compact models used for this purpose.

This model, named 'FB-2019' for short, will be directly applied to the experimental data for polyimide to describe its (n, κ) optical properties in the investigated electromagnetic wave range 190 – 25000 nm, corresponding to $\sim 6.53 - 0.05$ eV or $\sim 53000 - 400$ cm^{-1} .

The model is now described in its formulas.

8.2.1 FB-2019 Model

The formulation of 2019 is a direct consequence of the large applicability of their older model developed in 1988 with regards to amorphous materials, semiconductors and dielectrics, which was based on simple absorption models of quantum mechanics. The details of the derivation of the model can be found in the original paper [63], but in this chapter the latest model is presented.

The FB-2019 Model [68] applies to insulators, semiconductors, and generally materials that are not entirely crystals or metals, such as amorphous crystals and polymers.

The experimental basis is that for these kinds of materials, there exists an *energy band gap* E_g that, for energies $E > E_g$, identifies the onset of photons electronic absorption due to interband terms, whereas for $E < E_g$ either the materials is fully transparent or shows some optical response activity in the infrared due to excitations of phonons and/or molecular rotational modes. The FB-2019 model equations are detailed below, where the dispersion is written w.r.t energy $E = \hbar\omega$ [eV], and the *indicator function* $\mathbf{1}_{(x \in \Gamma)}$ of a set Γ is defined as 1 if $x \in \Gamma$, and 0 otherwise.

$$\kappa(E) = \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{A'_j E \mathbf{1}_{E \in (0, E_g)}}{E^2 - B'_j E + C'_j} + \sum_{j=1}^q \frac{A_j (E - E_g) \mathbf{1}_{E \in (E_g, +\infty)}}{E^2 - B_j E + C_j} \quad (29)$$

$$n(E) = n(\infty) + \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{(D'_j E + F'_j) \mathbf{1}_{E \in (0, E_g)}}{E^2 - B'_j E + C'_j} + \sum_{j=1}^q \frac{(D_j E + F_j) \mathbf{1}_{E \in (E_g, +\infty)}}{E^2 - B_j E + C_j} \quad (30)$$

Where the p -terms are those responsible for photon absorption below the bandgap E_g (phonons or rotational modes excitation terms), and the q -terms are those related to optical absorption happening at energies higher than the bandgap (interband transition terms). These terms will be described respectively as ‘phonon’ and interband terms.

The overall functions for the complex refractive index $\hat{N} = n + i\kappa$ as in FB-19 dispersion equations admit the two global free parameters E_g , $n(\infty)$, while each absorption band is defined by the following triplets: for the j -th phonon term, (A'_j, B'_j, C'_j) , whereas, for the j -th interband transition term, (A_j, B_j, C_j) . The units of these parameters are: A [eV], B [eV], C [eV²]. In general, the number of parameters for the model given p phonon terms and q interband ones is given by $2 + 3p + 3q$. These functions, so defined, satisfy automatically $\kappa(\infty) = 0$: this is thought by the authors to physically improve the older models.

The set of parameters in n is derived from the ones defining κ via the aforementioned Kramers-Kronig relations and they are defined by:

$$\begin{cases} D'_j = -\frac{A'_j B'_j}{2Q'_j} \\ F'_j = +\frac{A'_j C'_j}{Q'_j} \\ Q'_j = \left(C'_j - \frac{B'^2_j}{4}\right)^{1/2} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} D_j = +\frac{A_j}{Q_j} \left(E_g - \frac{B_j}{2}\right) \\ F_j = +\frac{A_j}{Q_j} \left(C_j - \frac{E_g B_j}{2}\right) \\ Q_j = \left(C_j - \frac{B^2_j}{4}\right)^{1/2} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

It is readily seen that the coefficients for terms lower than the bandgap are analogous to the interband terms if the E_g constant is set to zero, and also an important constraint arises in $C \geq B^2/4$ for all of the terms.

The parameters here defined possess a physical interpretation deeply connected to the quantum mechanical derivation of the older model from 1988. The A coefficient is proportional to the dipole matrix element squared of the transition of interest. In both interband and phonon summation terms, the numerator, either E or $(E - E_g)$, is proportional to the density of states associated with the transition. B is connected to the energy separation between initial and final state of the transition, and Q_j is equal to $\hbar/2\tau_j$ with τ_j being the lifetime of the j -th excited state of arrival during the transition. The energy band-gap E_g , as mentioned, is linked to the related onset of electronic transitions.

One important parameter is $n(\infty)$, which would be the refractive index at ‘infinite’ energy: in-fact this is taken as $1 + a$ where a is a mobile parameter which truly depends on the energy range under which the material is studied. Given a range of energies under which the material

(n, κ) are determined, the bigger the range size, the smaller a is expected to be. If the range width tends to infinity, $a \sim 0$ is expected, although generally $a \neq 0$ would be found to compensate all of the missing dispersion terms due to a limited spectral range.

Since the constants (A, B, C) - whether primed or not - are not immediately connected to spectral features during the analysis of experimental data, a new set of constants was defined, being $(E [\text{eV}], P, W [\text{eV}])$, representing respectively the $\kappa(E)$'s centre of the absorption band, its peak and its full width half maximum. These new definitions, other than being more intuitive to manoeuvre with, were found to be more agile during fitting procedures. For the set of coefficients representing the phonon terms below the energy gap, the following mapping is an exact bijection between (A'_j, B'_j, C'_j) and the newer (E'_j, P'_j, W'_j) .

$$\begin{cases} E'_j = (C'_j)^{1/2} \\ P'_j = \frac{A'_j}{2(C'_j)^{1/2} - B'_j} \\ W'_j = \left[(B'_j - 4(C'_j)^{1/2})^2 - 4C'_j \right]^{1/2} \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} C'_j = (E'_j)^2 \\ B'_j = 4E'_j - (W_j'^2 + 4E_j'^2)^{1/2} \\ A_j = P'_j \left[(W_j'^2 + 4E_j'^2)^{1/2} - 2E'_j \right] \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

Although these were perfectly defined, the same does not hold true for the interband terms. Again, for them it is possible to exactly define the energy centre of the absorption band, the peak value and the half-width of the j -th interband term in the sum as follows:

$$\begin{cases} E_{j\text{-exact}} = E_g + (C_j - B_j E_g + E_g^2)^{1/2} \\ P_{j\text{-exact}} = \frac{A_j (C_j - B_j E_g + E_g^2)^{1/2}}{E_{j\text{-exact}}^2 - B_j E_{j\text{-exact}} + C_j} \\ W_{j\text{-exact}} = \left[(B_j - 4(C_j)^{1/2})^2 - 4C_j \right]^{1/2} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

In which E_g clearly appears. It is very hard to invert this transformation to express (A_j, B_j, C_j) exactly as functions of $(E_{j\text{-exact}}, P_{j\text{-exact}}, W_{j\text{-exact}})$ - the exact bijection would be a very complex set of long and tedious equations, so these were discarded. An approximate form of mapping preserving the overall meaning of energy-peak, peak value and width parameters is employed, enabling the use of (E_j, P_j, W_j) 's during the fit procedure, from which the coefficients (A_j, B_j, C_j) in the model can be simply calculated as follows:

$$(E_j, P_j, W_j) \implies \begin{cases} C_j = (E_j)^2 - (W_j/2.426)^2 \\ B_j = 4(C_j)^{1/2} - (W_j^2 + 4C_j)^{1/2} \\ A_j = P_j \frac{E_j^2 - B_j E_j + C_j}{\sqrt{E_g^2 - B_j E_g + C_j}} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

The model for metals is now introduced.

8.2.2 FB-2021 Model

The model here discussed applies to metals, and summarises the information from the reference article [69]. This model was not used to analyse transmission data but was only used once to fit for experimental data of available n and κ of aluminium in literature.

From a physical standpoint, there is no energy bandgap in metals since this would be representative of the energy difference between valence/core and conduction electronic bands, whose energies overlap. In contrast to the model for dielectrics, the experimental curves defining the dispersion ($n(E), \kappa(E)$) for metallic specimens show no sharp rise in optical absorption, nor wide regions of transparency: κ is always greater than zero and occasionally shows local minima in the curve. The model is developed to describe three different mechanisms: the intraband electron transitions, occurring without any energy threshold; the interband electron transitions, each one depending on some characteristic energy threshold, and, in the end, a third term describing the inelastic collisions of electrons, which are expected to be of premium importance in the optical interactions in metals.

The expression of the FB-2021 model is here detailed, where again the dispersion is described with respect to the *energy* variable E [eV].

$$\kappa(E) = \sum_{j=1}^p \left[\frac{A'_j E}{E^2 + C'_j} \right] + \sum_{j=1}^q \left[\frac{A_j (E - X_j)^2}{E^2 - B_j E + C_j} - A_j \right] \quad (35)$$

$$n(E) = n(\infty) + \sum_{j=1}^p \left[\frac{A'_j (C'_j)^{1/2}}{E^2 + C'_j} \right] + \sum_{j=1}^q \left[\frac{(D_j E + F_j)}{E^2 - B_j E + C_j} \right] \quad (36)$$

Here there are the three terms as described before. The first term, present in the p -terms defining κ are the *inelastic* terms which only truly depend on the parameters (A'_j, C'_j) . This set of terms is the most responsible for the interaction with infrared light. As regards κ 's q -terms, these fall in two distinct kinds of transitions. The first one is the *intraband* transition, which has an energy threshold $X_j = 0$ and is defined solely by the triplet (A_j, B_j, C_j) , whereas the second kind of terms is given by the *interband* transition ones, satisfying $X_j \neq 0$ and described by the tetrad (A_j, B_j, C_j, X_j) . The units of these parameters are as earlier in the 2019 model, with X_j being analogous to E_g and measured in eV, the only difference being in the inelastic collision terms, where the A'_j 's have eV units instead of being dimensionless. If during a fit analysis, q inelastic collisional terms, p_{inter} interband terms and p_{intra} intraband terms are employed, then coupled with $n(\infty)$ the total amount of parameters is $1 + 2q + 3q_{\text{intra}} + 4q_{\text{inter}}$.

The set of parameters in n is derived again from the ones defining κ via the previously

mentioned Kramers-Kronig relations, and they are defined by:

$$\begin{cases} D_j = +\frac{A_j}{Q_j} \left(-\frac{B_j^2}{2} + B_j X_j - X_j^2 + C_j \right) \\ F_j = +\frac{A_j}{Q_j} \left((X_j^2 + C_j) \frac{B_j}{2} - 2X_j C_j \right) \\ Q_j = \left(C_j - \frac{B_j^2}{4} \right)^{1/2} \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

The physical interpretation of these parameters is closely related to that of FB-2019. In particular, for the q -terms, the A 's are probability terms, the B 's are energy differences, and the Q 's are related to lifetimes, the X 's are energies characteristic of the transitions. Similar interpretations hold true for the inelastic collision terms, where again each A'_j is (proportional to) a probability factor and a lifetime meaning is attributed to $C'_j = (\hbar/2\tau'_j)^2$. The significance of $n(\infty)$ is, once more, linked to the finiteness of the spectral range of analysis (which would make it depart from 1).

In this case, as well different parameters are employable to perform fit procedures, being more understandable in terms of spectral features. For the parameters of the inelastic terms (A'_j, C'_j) a simple new set of parameters (E'_j, P'_j) can be used, symbolising the peak position and peak value contribution to the sum defining κ , as defined here.

$$\begin{cases} E'_j = +\sqrt{C'_j} \\ P'_j = +\frac{A'_j}{2\sqrt{C'_j}} \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} A'_j = 2E'_j P'_j \\ C'_j = E'^2_j \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

For the parameters of the intraband terms (A_j, B_j, C_j) a simple new set of parameters (E_j, P_j, W_j) can be defined for peak positions, peak value and half-width, as follows.

$$\begin{cases} E_j = \frac{2C_j}{B_j} \\ P_j = \frac{A_j B_j^2}{4C_j - B_j^2} \\ W_j = \frac{[(B_j^2 - 8C_j)(B_j^2 - 4C_j)]^{1/2}}{B_j} \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} A_j = -P_j + \frac{2E_j P_j}{3E_j - (E_j^2 + W_j^2)^{1/2}} \\ B_j = 3E_j - (E_j^2 + W_j^2)^{1/2} \\ C_j = 0.5 \cdot (3E_j^2 - E_j (E_j^2 + W_j^2)^{1/2}) \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

No useful new set of terms or bijections were found for the set of parameters in the case of interband quadruplets (A_j, B_j, C_j, X_j)'s. The main transmission model for MTFs will be described in its entirety in the next section.

8.3 Transmission model: Transfer-Matrix Method

As a last part in the modelling sections, it is important to describe the whole transmission model employed for the MTFs. The following description is proven and detailed in the famous Born's Optics treatment [54, Chap. 1.6], as well as research papers in the field of thin films which successfully applied the formulas, such as in Barbera et al. [71]. The following method is known in optics literature as the Transfer-Matrix Method (TMM), and it gives a way to calculate the transmission and reflection of a MTF with normal incidence of radiation: this is an important detail since it neglects any dependence on the polarisation of the light, which would be taken into account in the case of generic incidence at an angle with respect to the layers' surfaces. The proof directly is derived from Maxwell's equations 11-14 and the related Fresnel equations, and the main hypothesis is to assume that each layer is *homogeneous*, that is both n and κ are constant within a layer: eventual gradients of the dielectric constant $\partial\epsilon/\partial z$ in the direction of propagation would require a different treatment than this one, such as the one proposed by Born [54, pp. 62-63].

If we are to study a given MTF so described: $X_1 - d_1 / (\dots) / X_m - d_m$, made of m consecutive layers, each one homogeneously made with the material X_j , described by its optical constants $(n_j(E), \kappa_j(E))$, and with exact thickness d_j , then it is possible to summarise the normal incidence transmittance and reflectance properties of the whole multi-layer, taking into account even the multiple reflections in between the layers and the possibility of constructive and destructive interference, by the clever usage of matrices. For this purpose, each j -th layer is characterised by a 2×2 unitary *characteristic matrix* \mathbf{M}_j , and that of the whole stratified medium, \mathbf{M} , is the product of the single matrices of each layer (in the order of the stratification).

$$\mathbf{M} = \prod_{j=1}^m \mathbf{M}_j \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{M}_j = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\delta_j) & i \sin(\delta_j)/\eta_j \\ i \eta_j \sin(\delta_j) & \cos(\delta_j) \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

With $\eta_j = n_j - i\kappa_j$ being the complex refractive index of the layer - with the *minus* notation⁵ - and $\delta_j = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_j d_j$ being the classical optical depth associated with the layer and concerning an electromagnetic wave of vacuum wavelength λ . The matrix elements of \mathbf{M} are calculated at each λ or E , and generally, they are $\begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} \end{bmatrix}$ as per usual linear algebra notation.

Two more media need to be described: the *incident* medium with complex refractive

⁵This notation would apply to electric fields as in eq. 19 having inverted the sign of the exponential argument, hence the plane wave solution would be $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 \exp(i(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \phi_0))$ with $\|\mathbf{k}\| = \eta\omega/c$.

index η_{inc} , from which the incoming wave is originated, and the exit medium, described by η_{exit} , which is traversed by the transmitted wave. Then, the amplitude of the transmission and reflection coefficients t and r are given by:

$$t = \frac{2\eta_{\text{inc}}}{(X + W) + i(Y + V)} \quad \text{and} \quad r = \frac{(X - W) + i(Y - V)}{(X + W) + i(Y + V)} \quad (41)$$

Where the quantities X , Y , W and V are defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= n_{\text{exit}} M_{11} - i n_{\text{inc}} \kappa_{\text{exit}} M_{12} & Y &= -i n_{\text{inc}} n_{\text{exit}} M_{12} \\ W &= n_{\text{exit}} M_{22} & V &= -i M_{21} - \kappa_{\text{exit}} M_{22} \end{aligned}$$

In a simplified case where the incoming and exit medium are made of air (or near vacuum), with approximately $\kappa \simeq 0$ and $n \simeq 1$, these simplify to:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= M_{11} & Y &= -i M_{12} \\ W &= M_{22} & V &= -i M_{21} \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the transmittance and reflectance of the whole stratified medium is given by - with $|z|$ being the module of the complex number z :

$$T = \frac{n_{\text{exit}}}{n_{\text{inc}}} |t|^2 \quad \text{and} \quad R = |r|^2 \quad (42)$$

As a consequence, provided that the thicknesses and the optical constants of each layer are known, it is possible to calculate the transmittance of any stratified structure. These formulas are inherently complex but there is a simple case scenario that is most informative: let the filter of interest be a monolayer which is also non-absorbing $\kappa = 0$ in a known region. Then, in such region, the transmission can be calculated exactly using only the optical depth $\delta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} nd$ and the refractive index n , and it would be as follows:

$$T = \frac{2n^2}{2n^2 + \sin^2(\delta) (n + 1)^2 (n - 1)^2} \quad (43)$$

The value of the transmission exhibits peaks - where $T = 1$ and $\delta = p\pi$ - and valleys with $T = T_{\text{min}}$, $\delta = (2p + 1)\frac{\pi}{2}$ and $p \in \mathbb{Z}$, throughout the whole non-absorbing region: the emerging shape of the transmission is usually defined as the *interference bands* and one example of this feature is clearly evident in the experimental data of the PI - 415 sample in fig. 24 - where, obviously, energy $E = hc/\lambda$ is used instead of wavelength. Knowing the transmission value of a valley, and the relative position of the two adjacent peaks λ_1 and λ_2 one can infer the value of the index of refraction n and the thickness of the layer d by means of the following relations.

$$n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T_{\text{min}}}} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sqrt{T_{\text{min}}}} - 1} \quad \text{and} \quad d = 2n \left| \frac{1}{\lambda_1} - \frac{1}{\lambda_2} \right|^{-1} \quad (44)$$

Clearly, these pieces of information are point-wise, while the entire transmittance spectrum $T(\lambda)$ is more informative with regards to n and κ than the sole interference bands.

9 Analysis of the polyimide samples

9.1 Protocol description

The process of analysis of the polyimide samples is now detailed. The idea is to completely characterise (n, κ) of polyimide in all three cases at our disposal, PI-415, PI-150 and PI-45, and in the investigated electromagnetic range 190 – 25000 nm via the use of FB-2019 model as described in sec. 8.2.1, and the employment of Python scripts and algorithms in order to assess the best-fit parameters for the model.

The very first step was to have an initial (even crude) model developed on the existing literature, such as in Cavadi et al.[72], and the process of developing initial parameters was aided by visual cues thanks to the use of much easier parameters (E_j, P_j, W_j) that literally transcribe to peak position, peak value and half-width of an absorbing band, as defined in equations 32 and 34: the use of an interactive GUI (provided by U. Lo Cicero) in combination with the Python scripts proved essential in assessing the mentioned initial parameters. The fit procedure is built upon the Levenberg-Marquardt non-linear least square curve fitting regression algorithm, used for the direct minimisation of the sum of squares of the *residual* function quantity, either defined in relative or difference mode as follows:

$$\text{Res}(E) = T_{\text{model}}(E) - T_{\text{data}}(E) \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Res} = \frac{T_{\text{model}}(E) - T_{\text{data}}(E)}{T_{\text{data}}(E)}$$

Uses of either difference or relative ratio modes were evaluated with respect to the dynamical range of T_{data} in the region of interest.

With regards to the complete definition of the parameter space, this includes parameters of the FB-2019 model chosen for PI: E_g , $n(\infty)$, $p = 31$ ‘phonon’ term triplets (A_j, B_j, C_j) , $q = 4$ interband terms triplets (A_j, B_j, C_j) , and the thickness d of the layer. The latter’s initial value can be estimated in the case of PI using the interference bands non-absorbing region covering $1000 \text{ nm} \lesssim \lambda \lesssim 5000 \text{ nm}$, or equivalently $1 \text{ eV} \lesssim E \lesssim 4 \text{ eV}$. Plots of the data (with visible interference bands) and the procedure to infer thicknesses from them are available in sections 7 and 8.3. Examples of plots describing these features are in the Experimental data section.

Since the parameter space’s dimension is 108, it would be very complex to fit the variables all together. The developed protocol to extract best-fit parameter models is detailed, built upon the principle that the parameters are fit in regions where their small variations have the most impact on the modelled transmission curve:

- The first step, to improve the crude initial model, is a fit on the thickness parameter d alone, performed in the region (1, 4) eV, in order to get a value of the thickness representative of the interference bands in the non-absorbing region
- A fit of the q interband parameters follows, along with the energy gap E_g , in the UV-Vis region (2.9, 6.526) eV
- A third important aspect is to fit the other p ‘phonon’ parameters in the complementary (mostly) infrared region (0.04956, 2.9) eV
- Then, the most influential global parameters E_g and $n(\infty)$ are fit in the whole region (0.04956, 6.526) eV
- If the model could be improved by adding particular absorption bands (or removing some), the changes are applied and the protocol is done again from scratch with the newer set of initial parameters
- As a final touch, the thickness d is fit again with the model alongside E_g in the spectral region (0.5, 4) eV. This fit will polish the best-fit values and it is particularly used to extract the statistical uncertainty associated with the variable.

When the uncertainties resulting from the fit were deemed ‘unphysical’, a different approach - either conducted via a Bayesian method or a random sampling technique - was employed to provide more meaningful uncertainty parameters. Further details about the methods to infer uncertainties in the algorithm are also provided in appendix C.

Virtually the same procedure is applied to all three polyimide samples, thus possibly extracting three different models of polyimide. Two different approaches might be considered: either one model for polyimide is used, e.g. the best-fit model obtained for PI – 415, which is then used to infer the thicknesses for all three samples, or three models are developed separately. It was found out that the former approach worked well in the IR region, but it did not work properly in the UV-Vis region (higher than the bandgap E_g) worsening considerably the residuals for other samples, hinting at the possibility that the PI – 150 and PI – 45 had different information to be extracted in this region. This is probably connected to the fact that sample PI – 415 had a very noisy measure in the UV-Vis region as visible in the logarithmic scale inset of fig. 24, at the resolution limit of the Spectrum 3 instrument, while the same did not occur with the others (figures 20 and 22). Hence it was decided to simply output three models of polyimide, as obtained from the three samples, and then compare them directly in subsequent chapters.

All of the results and the data analyses will be presented, with the models of polyimide and graphs representing data vs model comparisons.

9.2 Data analysis and results

The results of the analyses are described in the following table. all three obtained models

Table 3: Best fit results on the monolayer polyimide samples after the fit procedure using the retrieved Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 models, fitting for the thicknesses of each polymer layer. All of the parameters were obtained with the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, while the computational and statistical uncertainties were calculated in the region (0.5, 4) eV - the region of interference bands. Three times the 1σ statistical error is given as uncertainty to the thickness.

Sample Id. and Name	Derived Thickness [<i>nm</i>]
TF110-2476 (PI-45)	52.92 ± 0.09
TF110-2482 (PI-150)	163.9 ± 0.3
TF110-2466 (PI-415)	424.8 ± 1.0

will be described and discussed, along with plots of the model transmittance versus experimental data. 31 phonon terms and 4 interband terms are used: of the 31 infrared absorption terms, two (the first one and the last one) are associated with the start and the end of the spectrum, whilst all of the other 29 terms are physically connected to observed absorption in the transmission spectra.

9.2.1 Model of PI-45 (TF110-2476)

Table 4 describes all of the coefficients needed for the FB-2019 model of the filter sample TF110-2476 (or PI-45) which were obtained via the fit procedure of the experimental data measured for this filter as in sec. 7.1.

Table 4: Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 parameters for polyimide ($C_{22}H_{10}N_2O_4$) as found in the modelling of sample TF110-2476 (PI-45). The parameters refer to formulas explained in section 8.2.1. This model is connected to figures 33 and 34, which showcase its performance in fitting the (PI-45) transmission data.

Number of Terms in the Sum for Calculation	E_g (eV)	A_j (eV)	B_j (eV)	C_j (eV ²)	$n(\infty)$
p = 31	3.069	3.08269E-04	1.09623E-01	3.29063E-03	1.431
	//	2.59354E-05	1.25604E-01	3.96900E-03	//
		1.22717E-09	1.36404E-01	4.65151E-03	
		2.16994E-05	1.37638E-01	4.76100E-03	
		4.89233E-06	1.44567E-01	5.24987E-03	
		8.53281E-06	1.59431E-01	6.37954E-03	
		4.51832E-08	1.66648E-01	6.94306E-03	
		2.46791E-06	1.72936E-01	7.47844E-03	
		7.77312E-07	1.83288E-01	8.39899E-03	
		6.43480E-08	1.86092E-01	8.65774E-03	
		5.36597E-07	1.89812E-01	9.00810E-03	
		1.94759E-08	1.97301E-01	9.73202E-03	
		1.91042E-06	2.06727E-01	1.06852E-02	
		1.23657E-05	2.08258E-01	1.08679E-02	
		1.48111E-06	2.23194E-01	1.24601E-02	
		3.16597E-07	2.52550E-01	1.59476E-02	
		5.89347E-06	2.68266E-01	1.79978E-02	
		5.12921E-08	2.72627E-01	1.85818E-02	
		1.42157E-06	2.77981E-01	1.93210E-02	
		1.22131E-07	2.91948E-01	2.13093E-02	
		8.22618E-07	3.03048E-01	2.29607E-02	

Table 4: (Continued)

Number of Terms in the Sum for Calculation	E_g (eV)	A_j (eV)	B_j (eV)	C_j (eV ²)	$n(\infty)$
		5.44522E-06	3.13403E-01	2.45756E-02	
		1.84945E-05	3.37417E-01	2.84668E-02	
		9.44211E-07	3.52923E-01	3.11410E-02	
		1.77162E-06	3.75896E-01	3.53252E-02	
		6.71813E-06	4.00033E-01	4.00188E-02	
		4.93163E-06	4.25709E-01	4.53090E-02	
		8.54366E-07	4.28916E-01	4.59931E-02	
		4.89590E-07	4.40070E-01	4.84158E-02	
		7.29676E-04	7.70562E-01	1.58404E-01	
		3.51056E-04	1.49318E+01	5.57400E+01	
q = 4		1.38256E-01	8.43505E+00	1.81252E+01	
		4.84555E-01	9.62495E+00	2.61406E+01	
		1.17067E-02	1.27991E+01	4.11205E+01	
		3.00555E-03	6.89834E+00	1.19294E+01	

This model fits the collected data very well with a best-fit thickness for the PI layer of: 52.92 ± 0.09 nm as described in table 3. The value is not compatible with the nominal value 46.9 nm provided by the manufacturer, being 6.0 nm off. A visual representation for the fit's goodness is briefly displayed in the graph of the transmittance model, as to clearly mark the pros of the model, in figures 33 and 34. The $(n(E), \kappa(E))$ model arising from the PI-150 set of best fit parameters will be described in chapter 9.3.

Figure 33: Transmittance versus Model comparison for sample TF110-2476 (PI-45), in linear- T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is (0.04956, 3.5) eV, the region of interference bands and of the bandgap at $E = E_g = 3.069$ eV. Residues are also shown (relative %), being (in module) always $\lesssim 4\%$. The bandgap's optical absorbance onset is fairly evident in a jump of the residual.

Figure 34: Transmittance versus Model comparison for sample TF110-2476 (PI-45), in log-scale T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is (3.5, 6.526) eV, the region of high UV-Vis absorbance. The residues are also shown (in relative %), and the model undulates around the data with at most being $\sim 3\%$ off.

9.2.2 Model of PI-150 (TF110-2482)

Table 5 describes all of the coefficients needed for the FB-2019 model of the filter sample TF110-2466 (or PI-415) obtained via fit procedure of the experimental data measured for this filter as in sec. 7.2.

Table 5: Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 parameters for polyimide ($C_{22}H_{10}N_2O_4$) as found in the modelling of sample TF110-2482 (PI-150). The parameters refer to formulas explained in section 8.2.1. This model is connected to figures 35 and 36, which showcase its performance in fitting the (PI-150) transmission data

Number of Terms in the Sum for Calculation	E_g (eV)	A_j (eV)	B_j (eV)	C_j (eV ²)	$n(\infty)$
p = 31	3.036	3.08269E-04	1.09623E-01	3.29063E-03	1.431
	//	5.67475E-07	1.31292E-01	4.30979E-03	//
		4.95394E-07	1.36522E-01	4.66011E-03	
		4.44897E-07	1.41413E-01	5.00033E-03	
		2.26984E-07	1.45716E-01	5.30887E-03	
		5.97067E-08	1.57863E-01	6.23042E-03	
		3.02862E-08	1.66973E-01	6.97008E-03	
		1.47237E-06	1.72889E-01	7.47360E-03	
		6.88071E-07	1.83033E-01	8.37554E-03	
		2.15624E-08	1.86393E-01	8.68568E-03	
		1.99632E-07	1.89612E-01	8.98856E-03	
		1.65477E-08	1.97303E-01	9.73222E-03	
		1.02163E-06	2.06160E-01	1.06261E-02	
		2.12041E-06	2.08113E-01	1.08301E-02	
		3.72579E-07	2.21052E-01	1.22167E-02	
		2.60208E-08	2.53113E-01	1.60167E-02	
		2.74753E-06	2.67473E-01	1.78888E-02	
		7.16347E-07	2.72097E-01	1.85112E-02	
		9.05427E-07	2.77988E-01	1.93210E-02	
		3.37440E-08	2.91990E-01	2.13148E-02	
		1.04839E-06	3.03272E-01	2.29950E-02	
		4.61988E-07	3.13787E-01	2.46176E-02	
		1.70420E-05	3.37167E-01	2.84239E-02	
		2.35666E-07	3.52567E-01	3.10764E-02	
		1.22571E-06	3.75891E-01	3.53241E-02	
		2.75837E-06	4.00694E-01	4.01481E-02	

Table 5: (Continued)

Number of Terms in the Sum for Calculation	$E_g(\text{eV})$	$A_j(\text{eV})$	$B_j(\text{eV})$	$C_j(\text{eV}^2)$	$n(\infty)$
		3.04608E-06	4.25391E-01	4.52404E-02	
		1.70102E-06	4.28623E-01	4.59305E-02	
		5.20853E-07	4.40072E-01	4.84163E-02	
		1.73280E-04	7.97228E-01	1.64557E-01	
		3.51056E-04	1.49318E+01	5.57400E+01	
q = 4		5.98532E-02	8.38933E+00	1.77992E+01	
		3.94354E-01	9.17197E+00	2.24064E+01	
		1.59069E-02	1.28237E+01	4.12972E+01	
		1.04157E-02	6.91632E+00	1.20257E+01	

This model fits the collected data very well with a best-fit thickness for the PI layer of: 163.9 ± 0.3 nm as described in table 3. The value is different from the nominal value 148.2 nm provided by the manufacturer, estimating an excess 15.7 nm. A visual representation for the fit's goodness is briefly displayed in the graph of the transmittance model, as to clearly mark the pros of the model, in figures 35 and 36. The $(n(E), \kappa(E))$ model arising from the PI-150 set of best fit parameters will be described in chapter 9.3.

Figure 35: Transmittance versus Model comparison for sample TF110-2482 (PI-150), in linear- T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is (0.04956, 3.5) eV, the region of interference bands and of the bandgap at $E = E_g = 3.036$ eV. Residues are also shown (relative %), being (in module) always $\lesssim 4\%$. The bandgap's optical absorbance onset is fairly evident in a jump of the residual.

Figure 36: Transmittance versus Model comparison for sample TF110-2482 (PI-150), in log-scale T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is (3.5, 6.526) eV, the region of very high UV-Vis absorbance. The residues are also shown (relative %), and the model undulates around the data with at most being $\sim 10\%$ off.

9.2.3 Model of PI-415 (TF110-2466)

Table 6 describes all of the coefficients needed for the FB-2019 model of the filter sample TF110-2466 (or PI-415) obtained via fit procedure of the experimental data measured for this filter as in sec. 7.3.

Table 6: Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 parameters for polyimide (C₂₂H₁₀N₂O₄) as found in the modelling of sample TF110-2466 (PI-415). The parameters refer to formulas explained in section 8.2.1. This model is connected to figures 35 and 36, which showcase its performance in fitting the (PI-150) transmission data.

Number of Terms in the Sum for Calculation	E_g (eV)	A_j (eV)	B_j (eV)	C_j (eV ²)	$n(\infty)$
p = 31	2.924	3.38946E-04	1.10521E-01	3.37906E-03	1.431
	//	3.23493E-07	1.31302E-01	4.31026E-03	//
		4.31105E-07	1.36486E-01	4.65753E-03	
		2.51236E-07	1.41457E-01	5.00311E-03	
		1.11040E-07	1.45648E-01	5.30361E-03	
		1.80008E-08	1.57908E-01	6.23384E-03	
		3.54451E-08	1.66948E-01	6.96802E-03	
		1.47303E-06	1.72907E-01	7.47518E-03	
		6.84205E-07	1.82954E-01	8.36826E-03	
		1.47482E-08	1.86461E-01	8.69203E-03	
		1.99471E-07	1.89552E-01	8.98289E-03	
		1.65495E-08	1.97277E-01	9.72968E-03	
		1.04082E-06	2.06120E-01	1.06220E-02	
		2.25357E-06	2.08022E-01	1.08206E-02	
		5.40990E-07	2.20980E-01	1.22089E-02	
		5.68542E-08	2.53000E-01	1.60026E-02	
		3.89135E-06	2.67536E-01	1.78981E-02	
		4.13541E-07	2.72390E-01	1.85505E-02	
		1.08157E-06	2.77986E-01	1.93210E-02	
		6.36762E-08	2.91985E-01	2.13143E-02	
		1.21506E-06	3.03260E-01	2.29933E-02	
		4.74478E-07	3.13864E-01	2.46297E-02	
		1.78629E-05	3.36998E-01	2.83953E-02	
		2.50518E-07	3.52554E-01	3.10739E-02	
		1.24201E-06	3.75873E-01	3.53207E-02	
		2.02397E-06	4.00901E-01	4.01872E-02	

Table 6: (Continued)

Number of Terms in the Sum for Calculation	E_g (eV)	A_j (eV)	B_j (eV)	C_j (eV ²)	$n(\infty)$
		2.99644E-06	4.25412E-01	4.52449E-02	
		1.81671E-06	4.28703E-01	4.59477E-02	
		5.77808E-07	4.40044E-01	4.84103E-02	
		5.97153E-04	6.98640E-01	1.33467E-01	
		3.51132E-04	1.49318E+01	5.57400E+01	
q = 4		4.77818E-02	8.31070E+00	1.74333E+01	
		4.40537E-01	9.20576E+00	2.28961E+01	
		8.65429E-03	1.25723E+01	3.97181E+01	
		4.38685E-03	6.97688E+00	1.22102E+01	

This model fits the collected data very well with a best-fit thickness for the PI layer of: 424.8 ± 1.0 nm as was described in table 3. The value is higher than the nominal value 415.2 nm provided by the manufacturer by 9.6 nm. A visual representation of the fit's goodness is briefly displayed in the graph of the transmittance model, as to clearly mark the pros of the model, in figures 37 and 38. The $(n(E), \kappa(E))$ model arising from the PI-415 set of best fit parameters will be described in chapter 9.3.

Figure 37: Transmittance versus Model comparison for sample TF110-2466 (PI-415), in linear- T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is (0.04956, 2) eV, the region of interference bands. Residues are also shown (relative %), being always less than 4%.

Figure 38: Transmittance versus Model comparison for sample TF110-2466 (PI-415), in log-scale T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is (2, 6.526) eV, the region of very high UV-Vis absorbance. The residues are also shown (relative %), and the model scatters around the data with at most being $\sim 20\%$ off.

9.3 Analysis and comparison between PI models

A comparison can be done between the $(n(E), \kappa(E))$ resulting from the best-fit parameters found and listed in the sections above. Here is a comprehensive graph depicting all the three models.

As can be noticed, the three graphs are similar but show distinct features either at the start or at the end of the spectrum. At the start, the PI-45 model's extinction coefficient

Figure 39: Comparison of all three $(n(E), \kappa(E))$ models found for the different samples, PI-45, PI-150 and PI-415, in the whole region of experimental analysis, (0.04956, 6.525) eV. The trend is always the same in all three cases.

exhibits a broadening of the absorption band with peak energy $E_j = 0.0657$ eV as shown in the following figure, fig. 40, zooming on the region. The model of PI-45 is thought to be overestimating $\kappa(E)$ @ $E \sim 6.5 \times 10^{-2}$ eV due to the 0.5% T variability of the transmittance mentioned in section 7.1. This sample is virtually transparent, and the optical absorption bands in that part of the spectrum are modest, but whenever the transmission falls below $T \leq 99\%$, the model tries to explain this ‘unexpected’ absorption by artificially increasing the extinction coefficient (in this case, creating a bigger absorption band with high tails).

Conversely, at the higher energy end of the spectrum, the PI-415 model behaves differently than PI-150 and PI-45 ones. This might be due to the very high absorbances and the risk of reaching the end of the dynamical range of the instrument in the UV part experimental data for PI-415, as was hinted at in section 7.3, particularly since the extinction coefficient is estimated as lower than the other two samples at $E \sim 6$ eV. These features are shown in the following figure, fig. 41, zooming on the region. It would be of interest in the future to check whether the other discrepancies found between these models, such as the differences

Figure 40: Comparison of all three $(n(E), \kappa(E))$ models found for the different samples, PI-45, PI-150 and PI-415, in the region (0.04956, 0.1) eV. The PI-45 sample clearly joined the different absorption bands into a bigger one, changing the overall spectral shape of the extinction coefficient with respect to the other samples.

Figure 41: Comparison of all three $(n(E), \kappa(E))$ models found for the different samples, PI-45, PI-150 and PI-415, in the UV-Vis region (2, 6.525) eV. The PI-415 sample has a lower extinction coefficient at the end of the spectrum, while PI-150 and PI-45 mostly agree with each other. This could be due to the PI-415 sample reaching the upper absorbance limit of the dynamical range of the instrument.

in shape and trends of $\kappa(E)$ at $3 \text{ eV} \leq E \leq 6 \text{ eV}$ as seen in the figure above, are in any way related to differences arising from manufacturing processes by Luxel, or if those are only related to the computational approach adopted here. Discussions with the manufacturer, and possible attempts at analysing simulated transmission data could help pinpoint the accuracy of this method.

With regard to comparisons with the existing literature, the values found for the energy gap, $E_g \sim 3 \text{ eV}$ agree with the optical analyses of polyimide samples by Matsumoto et al. [73], that found wavelengths cut-offs in the optical transmission of $\lambda_c \simeq 400 \text{ nm} \Leftrightarrow E_c \simeq 3 \text{ eV}$. Moreover, the IR structure is almost a perfect match with the independent IR analysis of Luxel polyimide films performed by Zhang et al. [52], as shown in the following comparison picture.

Figure 42: Comparison between the optical constants (n, κ) the polyimide Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 models developed in this work (on the left), and the Lorentz-based model by Zhang et al. (on the right). The units on the left are eV, and on the right cm^{-1} , covering respectively the equivalent ranges $(0.2479, 0.062) \text{ eV}$ and $(2000, 500) \text{ cm}^{-1}$

It is possible to link the found absorption bands (noticeable in figure 42) to particular chemical bonds and traits, as was done by Dhakshnamoorthy et al. [53] during polyimide films studies. In their work, some of the bands are analogous to those found both in this thesis

and in Zhang et al. and they are: the band centred at $E \approx 0.2201$ eV linked to the asymmetric C=O stretching vibrational band; the absorption band at $E \approx 0.2124$ eV, linked to symmetric C=O stretching; the absorption peak at $E \approx 0.1714$ eV, associated with C–N stretching, and, finally, another absorption band at $E \approx 0.09237$ eV is linked to C=O bending. Any further considerations about this interesting topic lie outside the scope of this thesis.

Conclusively, the Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 model is well suited to describe the properties of thin film polymer materials such as Luxel polyimide, and the procedure here detailed is a good basis to proceed in that regard. Based on the analyses, and the features of the experimental data collected, both PI-415 and PI-150 (n, κ) models are thought to represent well polyimide optical behaviour in the infrared region, while both PI-45 and PI-150 (n, κ) models work well in the UV-Vis region. For this reason, the optical Forouhi-Bloomer model for PI-150 is taken as the reference model for future analyses of the aluminium-coated filters, which follow in the next sections.

10 Analysis of the PI/Al samples

10.1 Protocol description

Now the process of analysis of the aluminised filter samples is detailed. The aim of the following chapters is to properly model the MTFF samples whose transmission data was collected, that is the TF110-2475 (PI – 45/Al – 20), the TF110-2462 (PI – 45/Al – 30) and the TF110-2460 (PI – 150/Al – 30). As was mentioned in section 6, the formation of an amorphous alumina layer is expected on both surfaces of the metal layer: consequently, the transmission model will take into account that each MTFF is truly made of four layers, structured as $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1/\text{Al}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2/\text{PI}$, with each layer requiring an (n, κ) model for the application of the TMM. For a good model of polyimide, the Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 model deduced in section 9.2.2 is used. As for the models of Al and Al_2O_3 , models from the literature are employed, and their sources are specified in the subsequent chapters. A Forouhi-Bloomer 2021 model for the aluminium is also developed fitting for the available (n, κ) data, as a unrefined proof of concept for possible applications of the model, but interpolated values of the experimental data of ($n(E), \kappa(E)$) available from the literature were used in the model to estimate the layers the thicknesses.

As for the protocol itself, the quantities to be measured are $d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1}$, d_{Al} , $d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2}$, d_{PI} , and it is as follows :

- In order to find the first proper initial set of parameters for a good fit, a first fit is employed with initial values $d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1} = 0$, $d_{\text{Al}} = \text{nominal}$, $d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2} = 0$, $d_{\text{PI}} = \text{nominal}$, along with the constraint $d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1} = d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2} = d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$ as an initial guess that the oxide layers are symmetrically deployed around the aluminium. The fit is performed in difference mode for the residual, and it is performed in the UV-Vis-NIR part of the spectrum, (0.5, 6.526) eV
- An attempt is then made to improve the initial parameters, and a fit is performed in relative mode for the residual in the whole spectrum (0.04956, 6.526) eV. The resulting parameters are then used in the following phases.
- Once a good set of initial parameters ($d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1} = d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$, d_{Al} , $d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2} = d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$, d_{PI}) is found, another fit is performed on all four parameters ($d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1}$, d_{Al} , $d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2}$, d_{PI}) in the energy range (0.5, 6.526) eV without the constraint of equal oxide thicknesses, in difference mode.
- A fit is performed on the whole spectrum in relative mode to improve the set of values if such is the case.
- At last, once a very good set of parameters is found, a subsequent fit is evaluated, performed in relative mode in the UV-Vis-NIR range (0.5, 6.525) eV. This fit would provide both a concluding fine improvement and also the statistical uncertainties and correlations of the 4 parameters.

Again, more details on the exact way the fits are performed, and a schematic view of the Python code, are available in appendices C and B. The models for Al_2O_3 and Al are henceforth detailed.

10.2 Refractive index of Aluminium Oxide

The model of aluminium oxide Al_2O_3 , or *alumina* is important to be discussed, as it is intended to appear both at the air-exposed aluminium surface and at the interface between Al and PI in the MTFs of this work. There are many forms in which alumina appears: some of the crystal forms are $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (naturally found in minerals such as corundum, ruby and sapphire), but also δ , θ and $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ - differing in density and crystalline structure - but in the case of thermally and spontaneous oxide formation, it can also be in a porous and amorphous state, ($\text{am-Al}_2\text{O}_3$), without an entirely crystallised structure. Hence, it is important that this aspect is taken into account during the usage of an (n, κ) model for alumina, and the available data for analyses of thin films Al_2O_3 made it possible to develop a model in a very broad range from $0.000775 \mu\text{m}$ to $10000 \mu\text{m}$ covering the range needed in our investigation. Most of the experimental data of metals discussed here can be found in tabular form at <https://refractiveindex.info/> (last visited on 05/06/2022), and the original papers are quoted. The model uses the following data, going from higher energies to lower energies, where all of the articles analysed films of Al_2O_3 :

- From $0.000775 \mu\text{m}$ to $0.2066 \mu\text{m}$, data is by Hagemann et al. [57], based on the analysis of Al_2O_3 thin films
- From $0.405 \mu\text{m}$ to $1.54 \mu\text{m}$, data is taken by Kumar et al. [74] based on the analysis of Al_2O_3 thin films
- From $1.54 \mu\text{m}$ to $6.65 \mu\text{m}$, data is taken by Kischkat et al. [75] based on the analysis of Al_2O_3 thin films
- From $6.66 \mu\text{m}$ to $10000 \mu\text{m}$, data is taken by Zeidler et al. [76], whose analysis was performed on a pure synthetic corundum 3 mm thick, averaged between three sets of measurement.

It must be noted that the last set of experimental data would be representative of bulk properties of Al_2O_3 , not amorphous properties.

In the range of interest to us (from 0.04956 eV to 6.526 eV), this is how the model would appear. This model shows infrared absorption peaks whose central energies correspond to wavenumbers $\tilde{\nu}_1 \approx 450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\tilde{\nu}_2 \approx 600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is stated in the specialised reference by Tolstoy et al. [77, pp. 227-228, 533, 670] that, although bulk crystalline Al_2O_3 shows *phonon* absorption bands at $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{TO}} = 628.9 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{LO}} = 943.4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, these absorption bands⁶ could vary sensibly with the *porosity* of Al_2O_3 , shifting to lower values with increasing porosity:

⁶TO stands for *Transverse Optical* and LO for *Longitudinal Optical* phonon modes

Figure 43: Al_2O_3 ($n(E), \kappa(E)$) dispersion model used in this work, based on the data from the articles quoted in the list above in the range (0.01, 10) eV given in logarithmic- E -scale. Two structured absorption bands with peaks E_1, E_2 are visible in the ranges $E_1 \in (0.05, 0.06)$ eV and $E_2 \in (0.07, 0.08)$ eV.

consequently, the overall absorption shape can depend on the manufacturing mechanism and the conditions of oxidation. Another critical aspect is that the band-gap energy for am- Al_2O_3 is expected to be around 7 eV [49] or possibly lower, although the given graph would hint at the band-gap being closer to 9 eV. These aspects would require a more detailed experimental analysis for the optical and infrared properties of amorphous Al_2O_3 occurring on Luxel-aluminium, but they are not further considered in this work.

The model proposed is thought of as a starting point for oxide-evaluation via Infrared and UV-Vis transmission spectroscopy. The aluminium optical constants will now be addressed.

10.3 Refractive index of Aluminium

Similarly to the case of Al_2O_3 , a model for the pure metal Al needs to be developed in order to apply the transmission matrix method to our thin filters. Data for available literature was used, that made it possible to develop a model in a broad range from $0.000124 \mu\text{m}$ to

1240 μm covering the range needed in our investigation. As in the earlier section, the data is available at <https://refractiveindex.info/>, and the original papers are quoted. The model uses the following data, going from higher energies to lower energies, where all of the works analysed thin film Al films:

- From 0.000124 μm to 200 μm , data is by A. D. Rakić [78]
- From 248 μm to 1240 μm , data is by Hagemann et al. [57]

The model appears as follows in our range of experimental interest (from 0.04956 eV to 6.526 eV).

Figure 44: Al ($n(E), \kappa(E)$) dispersion model used in this work, based on the data from the articles quoted in the list above in the range (0.01, 10) eV given in logarithmic scales on both axes. The function appears smooth and increases highly in absorption in the infrared region, with only moderate absorption bands.

As an exercise, a Forouhi-Bloomer 2021 model was developed to fit the experimental (n, κ) data given above. A Python script was written, using the Levenberg-Marquardt non-linear least square curve fitting regression algorithm to minimise the residual quantity $|\hat{N}_{\text{model}} - \hat{N}_{\text{data}}|^2$, square of modulus of the residual between the modelled and the experimental indexes of refraction. The fit procedure of the parameters is performed for each set of interband, intraband and inelastic parameters described in sec. 8.2.2). The initial set of parameters for aluminium was taken directly by Forouhi and Bloomer [69]. The resulting best-fit model is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Example of fitting parameters A_j , B_j , C_j , X_j , A'_j , and C'_j for the experimental Al (n, κ) data described in the list above. The formulas detailing the use of these coefficients are found in sec. 8.2.2. The performance of the model is shown in the graph in figure 45.

Number of Terms 1st	A_j	B_j (eV)	C_j (eV) ²	X_j (eV)	Number of Terms 2nd	A'_j (eV)	C'_j (eV) ²
Sum					Sum		
q = 6	4.76985E-04	1.84021E+02	8.59809E+03	0.00000E+00	p = 3	2.17964E+00	1.69300E-07
	1.18569E-04	2.37355E+02	1.42108E+04	0.00000E+00		6.70661E+00	2.94124E-04
	1.55298E+00	2.95998E+00	2.22666E+00	1.37240E+00		4.11798E+00	1.43244E-02
	1.66959E+01	3.23993E+01	2.63966E+02	1.63376E+01			
	7.66744E-02	6.16645E+00	1.29776E+01	7.31431E+00			
	2.32429E-02	1.45850E+02	5.32000E+03	1.00000E-05			

Regardless, an interpolated version of the direct experimental data from the original sources is used for the other transmission models of PI/Al filters. Figure 45 shows a comparison between the data and the best-fit model.

Figure 45: Al ($n(E), \kappa(E)$) dispersion model used in this work obtained from experimental data as detailed in the list above, versus the Forouhi-Bloomer 2021 best-fit model of table 7, in the range (0.04, 7) eV and on a log-log scale. The model is almost a perfect match for the $\kappa(E)$ graph, but there is room for improvement in the UV-Vis range for the $n(E)$.

10.4 Data analysis and results

To summarise the hypotheses of the subsequent analyses, the following models and methods are employed:

- For the polyimide model, the FB-19 best-fit PI-150 model was chosen, as it is deemed to be the most appropriate in all of the regions of experimental importance in this work. The full model is displayed and listed in sec. 9.2.2, in table 5.
- The amorphous Al_2O_3 model, described in section 10.2, is obtained by merging experimental data from various works in literature dealing with thin films of aluminium oxide.
- For the aluminium Al model, an analogous model obtained mainly from the data by Hagemann and Rakić as described in section 10.3 is utilised.
- For the transmission model, the TMM method described in 8.3 is used.

The results are then described in table 8, as best fit thicknesses for each layer and a parameter of statistical uncertainty, following the protocol described in sec. 10.1. Graphs detailing each model and the respective residuals are displayed in the following sections.

Table 8: Best fit results on the ML aluminised polyimide samples after the fit procedure of the four thicknesses are listed. Three times the statistical error result from the fit is given as uncertainty to the thicknesses.

Sample ID/Name	$d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1}$ [nm]	d_{Al} [nm]	$d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2}$ [nm]	d_{PI} [nm]
TF110-2475 (PI-45/Al-20)	3.2 ± 1.6	12.40 ± 0.06	6.7 ± 1.1	48.1 ± 1.7
TF110-2462 (PI-45/Al-30)	5.9 ± 1.4	20.1 ± 0.08	6.6 ± 1.2	54.8 ± 1.5
TF110-2460 (PI-150/Al-30)	7.0 ± 1.1	27.9 ± 0.05	10.5 ± 0.9	190.0 ± 1.0

The resulting values can be compared to the nominal thickness data as furnished by the manufacturer. The nominal values were: for the PI-45/Al-20, 21.5 nm of Al and 42.7 nm of PI; for the PI-45/Al-30, 29.4 nm of Al and 47.4 nm of PI; and finally, for the PI-150/Al-30, 30.4 nm of Al and 157.8 nm of PI. Generally, the results of the inferred PI and Al match the order of magnitude of that provided by Luxel, although the aluminium is systematically underestimated, which is evidence for the formation of oxide layers, whereas the PI layers are overestimated.

To better understand the results, the output of the correlations between these variables as registered by the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm during the final part of the fit is given in table 9.

Table 9: Correlation between the variables that resulted in the best-fit thicknesses in table 8.

Correlation Element	PI-45/Al-20	PI-45/Al-30	PI-150/Al-30
$C(d_{\text{PI}}, d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1})$	0.940	0.933	0.758
$C(d_{\text{PI}}, d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2})$	-0.903	-0.911	-0.806
$C(d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1}, d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2})$	-0.849	-0.847	-0.687
$C(d_{\text{Al}}, d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#1})$	0.829	0.830	0.643
$C(d_{\text{Al}}, d_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\#2})$	-0.634	-0.647	-0.438
$C(d_{\text{PI}}, d_{\text{Al}})$	0.784	0.769	0.462

Such a high set of correlations suggest that the variables are not independent from each other during the fit procedure. Changing the initial conditions of the fits were also seen to directly affect the ending results for the oxide layers estimates, while the aluminium thickness was a sturdy parameter even with initial values changes. Clearly, both this and the correlations hint at systematic factors that affect the best-fit results. As a consequence, the resulting measures for the thicknesses, particularly the oxides, can be thought of as indicative, and possible different approaches will be discussed in section 10.4.4.

The graphs associated with the best-fit thicknesses in table 8 are showcased for each of the MTFE samples under analysis in the upcoming sections.

10.4.1 Model of PI-45/Al-20 (TF110-2475)

Here are displayed the data vs model plots for the aluminised sample with nominal thicknesses: 20 nm for aluminium and 45 nm for polyimide. The found thicknesses with the transmission matrix method analysis were: 12.40 nm of Al, 48.1 nm of PI and a total Al_2O_3 amount of 9.9 nm.

Figure 46: Comparison between the transmittance data and best-fit thicknesses model of table 8, for the sample TF110-2475 (Al – 20/PI – 45), in linear- T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is the full range, (0.04956, 6.526) eV. Residues are also shown in relative % unit: the model is at most $\sim 25\%$ off, with the exception of the mid-infrared, where the model underestimates the data by more than 50%.

Figure 47: Comparison between the transmittance data and best-fit thicknesses model of table 8, for the sample TF110-2475 (PI – 45/Al – 20), in logarithmic scales. The energy range displayed is the full range, (0.04956, 6.526) eV. The infrared portion is underestimated by about half an order of magnitude.

10.4.2 Model of PI-45/Al-30 (TF110-2462)

Here are displayed the data vs model plots for the aluminised sample with nominal thicknesses: 30 nm for aluminium and 45 nm for polyimide. The found thicknesses with the transmission matrix method analysis were: 20.1 nm of Al, 54.8 nm of PI and a total Al_2O_3 amount of 12.5 nm.

Figure 48: Comparison between the transmittance data and best-fit thicknesses model of table 8, for the sample TF110-2462 (PI – 45/Al – 30), in linear- T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is the full range, (0.04956, 6.526) eV. Residues are also shown in relative % unit: the model is at most $\sim 25\%$ off, except for the mid-infrared, where the model underestimates the data by more than 50%.

Figure 49: Comparison between the transmittance data and best-fit thicknesses model of table 8, for the sample TF110-2462 (PI – 45/Al – 30), in logarithmic scales. The energy range displayed is the full range, (0.04956, 6.526) eV. The infrared portion is underestimated by about half an order of magnitude.

10.4.3 Model of PI-150/AL-30 (TF110-2460)

Here are displayed the data vs model plots for the aluminised sample with nominal thicknesses: 30 nm for aluminium and 150 nm for polyimide. The found thicknesses with the transmission matrix method analysis were: 27.9 nm of Al, 190.0 nm of PI and a total Al_2O_3 amount of 17.5 nm.

Figure 50: Comparison between the transmittance data and best-fit thicknesses model of table 8, for the sample TF110-2460 (PI – 150/Al – 30), in linear- T -axis and log- E -axis. The energy range displayed is the full range, (0.04956, 6.526) eV. Residues are also shown in relative % unit: the model is at most $\sim 25\%$ off, except in the mid-infrared, where the model underestimates the data by more than 50%.

Figure 51: Comparison between the transmittance data and best-fit thicknesses model of table 8, for the sample TF110-2460 (PI – 150/Al – 30), in logarithmic scales. The energy range displayed is the full range, (0.04956, 6.526) eV. The infrared portion is underestimated by about half an order of magnitude.

A few ending remarks about the latter analyses are described, before delving into the conclusion of the thesis.

10.4.4 Remarks on the analyses

The fit models given in the last paragraphs had very similar traits. The models picked up the trend of the experimental curves in most of the energy range besides the infrared portion, where it was systematically off by more than 50%. There are several possible explanations for this occurring theme, but for short, these are signs of the need to refine the overall model.

- The underestimate in infrared absorption suggests that surface defects could play a non-negligible role in hindering the blocking efficiency of the filters. As a consequence, the effect of defects should be properly modelled, i.e. taking into consideration the defects expected to arise from the MTFs production techniques (briefly described in sec. 6) could result in explaining an excess IR transmission, improving the best-fit residuals in the process.
- Another possibility is that neither the used tabulated Al_2O_3 nor Al properly model the infrared absorption of the given MTFs. *Ad hoc* models should be developed using experimental data of naturally occurring Al_2O_3 layers generated on Al thin film made with production techniques similar to those used by Luxel. Properties such as the Al_2O_3 porosity can modify the optical property of the whole ML structure, as hinted at in section 10.2, and, in turn, this aspect would modify the optical properties of Al at the interface
- FT-IR procedures might introduce systematic errors at very high wavelengths, hence independent measures should be performed in MIR ranges to ensure that the data is clean of artefacts.
- Finally, the high correlations presented in table 9 suggest that the fit is not efficient at discriminating between the different parameters. Either other constraints need to be imposed, or a different strategy should be constructed to exploit the UV-Vis or infrared properties of polyimide, aluminium and amorphous aluminium oxide. For example, if a model was used for the amorphous Al_2O_3 layer, that better fit the oxide in Luxel films with absorption bands at particular frequencies, the overall efficiency of the fit procedure would be improved.

Overall, the transmission model built up for MTFs, though with some approximations - especially in the case of Al_2O_3 and Al treated with literature data, is capable to follow the trend of the measured transmission curves, and to quantitatively make estimates of the layer thicknesses which are in line with the manufacturer's specifications. The approach to deriving optical constants of a material by measuring the transmission of a few monolayer

samples of different thicknesses and using the FB-2019 and FB-2021 models to fit them is effective and provides good ingredients for the ML transmission model.

11 Conclusions

During this thesis project, the main purpose was to both characterise experimentally the UV, optical and NIR-MIR transmission of multilayer thin film filters (MTFFs) currently expected to be employed on the Athena X-ray astrophysics space mission, and to also develop computational protocols suitable for retrieving a sensible model of their transmittance.

The Athena mission, to be launched approximately in 2035, was selected by ESA to pursue the science theme of the Hot and Energetic Universe. The project will study some of the most violent and energetic phenomena in the universe: hot gas in between clusters of galaxies, accretion in SMBHs and AGNs activity, supernova remnants, stellar winds of massive stars and much more. The science goals are the backbone of the mission, being part of the mission proposal which dates back to 2013, and they are all fundamentally open questions which require an observatory as powerful as Athena to be tackled. These science goals drive the requirements and performance parameters of the instruments aboard the mission. The optical and thermal blocking filters, the subject of this work, need to ensure high enough optical protection and thermal shielding of the detectors, all in all with the purpose to ensure that the incoming X-rays are decoded with negligible energy resolution degradation and low background noise. The study and modelling of these filters are valuable in assessing the filters' compliance with the driving requirements.

Six samples were analysed, three monolayer polyimide (PI) filter samples with nominal thicknesses of about 45, 150 and 415 nm, and three aluminised polyimide samples (PI/Al), whose nominal thicknesses were about 45/20, 45/30 and 150/30, all of them manufactured by Luxel Corporation. The latter two aluminised polyimide samples are representative of the current filters baseline design of Athena, although re-scaled down to a 10.2 mm aperture sample size.

The main reasons for the employment of polyimide and aluminium filters in X-ray telescopes, directly assessed and explored during this work, are also connected to their reliability, structural resistance, IR-reflectance and UV-absorbance properties. A legacy to their success is their usage in very important missions such as Chandra and XMM-Newton, as of today still working and giving birth to quality scientific content. These aspects were reviewed to give a full account of the environment encapsulating the use of PI/Al MTFFs, and also to introduce the aspect of those X-ray missions themselves, which share with Athena many of their essential characteristics.

The filters transmission was to be characterised in the spectral range 190 nm ÷ 25000 nm,

and for this purpose two recently acquired spectrometers in the laboratories of INAF-OAPA were employed: the Spectrum 3, an FT-IR spectrometer, and the Lambda 1050+, a UV-Vis-NIR, both from Perkin Elmer, and respectively used in the sub-ranges 190 nm ÷ 3300 nm and 1500 nm ÷ 25000 nm. As part of my thesis work I have participated in the commissioning of the instruments, testing their capabilities, and setting up optimal collection parameters. Experimental transmittance plots were obtained for all the selected filter samples, and their features were explored, and the resulting plots were reported.

The polyimide filters showed characteristic signs of interference bands: these were of utmost importance in the estimation of the filter thicknesses. The PI filters also exhibited quite a dense number of absorption bands in the infrared spectrum, particularly in the range 5000 nm–25000 nm, and the data obtained was generally clean of artefacts, with the exception of a few systematic features - particularly, the high absorption in the UV for the PI-415, and the variability $\Delta T \sim 0.05\%$ in the transmittance measurements of the PI-45 in the MIR band. The PI/Al samples transmittance data were also analysed qualitatively, and they generally had smoother curves than their monolayer counterparts. The main features were the high absorbance in infrared, and the increase of noise levels where the infrared transmission was very low for each instrument.

An important aspect was to develop an initial working optical model for these filters and to question its reliability in inferring parameters such as thicknesses. The Transfer Matrix Method (TMM) was used as a means to obtain the transmittance of a given MTF, requiring the thicknesses and the optical constants (n and κ) of each layer composing the filter, assuming homogeneity and the absence of gradients in the optical properties. For the polyimide samples, a simple monolayer model was employed, while for the PI/Al bilayers, a four-layer model was employed to take into account the build-up of amorphous aluminium oxide Al_2O_3 both at the exposed surface of aluminium and at the interface with the polymer.

The Forouhi-Bloomer 2019 model for dielectrics and amorphous materials was introduced and employed to analyse the available transmittance curves of the PI samples. For completeness, the FB-2021 model for metals was introduced, although not employed in the scripts analysing the filters' data. A fit procedure and protocol were built, to model the data from the mono-layer PI transmittance curves, retrieving the optical constants (in terms of FB-2019 coefficients) and the thickness of the sample. The resulting n and κ models were reported both in the form of plots and respective tables of FB-19 coefficients and parameters - one for each sample. Their corresponding transmittance model vs data and residual plots were reported, overall with encouraging results, only being a few %s off on average. In general,

the optical properties of polyimide derived from the three data samples agreed well, besides some minor aspects connected to the systematic spectral features mentioned above. The fit results also provided estimates of the thicknesses of the polyimide layers, agreeing quite well with the nominal thicknesses provided by the manufacturer. Statistical uncertainties were also provided.

Having estimated a good model for the polyimide monolayers, we proceeded with the analysis of PI/Al bilayers in order to infer the thicknesses. The Al and Al₂O₃ n 's and κ 's used for the modelling of the aluminised samples were taken from the existing literature of available studies of thin films. With the models of each component, a protocol and fit procedure was also described to estimate the Al, the PI, and the two am-Al₂O₃ layer thicknesses. The fit protocol resulted in estimating the thicknesses of each part of the layer, and the residuals of the model minus data this time were not as promising, with the residuals surpassing at times 20%. Particularly, the model underestimated the aluminised MTFs infrared transmittance by an average of 50%. Otherwise, the overall trend was followed. The best-fit thicknesses were reported along with their respective plots, along with estimated statistical uncertainties, and also the correlation matrix was given as a way to judge the fit's wellness. For the most part these parameters were highly correlated, and the oxide layers' thicknesses estimates depended heavily on the initial conditions of the fits.

In general, the main research question was addressed. A protocol was developed in this work, which functioned very well in the case of the monolayer samples, resulting in a model with very close residues with respect to the data and good estimates on the retrieved thicknesses and optical constants for PI. On a basic level it worked also for the aluminised polymer samples, it followed the trend of the transmission data and gave reliable thickness estimates of Al and PI layers, albeit with indicative estimates for oxide thickness layers. The results of this work, and the learnt knowledge about the models weaknesses will be a basis for ensuing further analyses.

As for future prospects, there is much room for improvement. On the experimental side, independent measurements with other techniques should be employed to estimate the oxide layer content in the bilayers: moreover, the impact of the history of measurements on the filters on their optical properties should be assessed, as some defects may in principle arise directly from some kind of experiments (i.e. synchrotron beamlines irradiation). From a modelling perspective, improvements to the model should be considered, to implement the effects of defects and possibly of gradients in the optical constants, but also to narrow down the exact behaviour of the optical constants of Al and am-Al₂O₃ in nanometric films

produced with techniques such as those employed by Luxel. Constrains to the models should be assessed: one way could be by doing analogue studies such as those done in this work to a large number of independent aluminium and aluminium/polymer thin films, manufactured in the same fashion as Luxel, which could result, by statistical analyses, in identifying the correct Al or am-Al₂O₃ models, either modelled by FB-21 and FB-19 models respectively or by analogues. At last, in respect of the computational side, mock simulations and analysis of synthetic data with the same (or similar) specifications as the spectrometers used in this work and with a given set of initial known optical constants (i.e. modelled PI/Al with the oxide layers) could be considered, in order to assess more thoroughly the reliability of the retrieved optical constants by the algorithm.

Appendices

A Data collection setup parameters

This appendix is a placeholder for the repetitive information regarding the instrumental parameters used to collect the raw data as described in section 7. A summary of these parameters was given in the sections describing the Lambda 1050+ and Spectrum 3 instruments (sec. 5.1 and 5.2), but in some cases the measurements had slight differences for the data collection parameters with respect to those parameters mentioned in such chapters, and knowing the exact parameters may be of use for future improvements and/or for repeatability studies. Also, the following ranges were decided as they are to minimise the effect of instrument changes since the measurements obtained with Spectrum 3 and Lambda usually provided some useful overlap. In the following, for each filter, the complete disjoint ranges making up the shown transmission dataset are detailed along with the exact parameters connected with them. As further pieces of information, all of the measurements performed with Spectrum 3 were obtained as an average of three different measures (with the same setup parameters) whose difference consisted in a rotation of the sample at each session, and they all utilised the following advanced settings: CO₂/H₂O automatic correction put on, Phase Correction set as ‘Magnitude’ and Apodization set as ‘Strong’.

PI-45 (TF110-2476), section 7.1

- In the range 190 – 2500 nm, the measures were obtained with the Lambda 1050+, with: data interval 1 nm; common beam mask (CBM) 50%; UV/Vis slit width (spectral) 5 nm; UV/Vis detector gain set on Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.4 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.0; NIR slit width on Servo, and NIR detector response 2 s.
- In the range 2500.25 – 25000 nm, associated with Spectrum 3, the adopted instrumental parameters were: scan speed (SS) 0.2 cm s⁻¹; resolution 4 cm⁻¹; data interval (i.e. pitch) 0.4 cm⁻¹ and accumulation 128 scans.

PI-150 (TF110-2482), section 7.2, same ranges and parameters as the PI-45 case.

PI-415 (TF110-2466), section 7.3

- In the range 190 – 350 nm the measure was done with the Lambda 1050+ instrument and the data collection settings for the measure were: data interval 2 nm; CBM 30%; UV/Vis slit width 2 nm; UV/Vis detector gain Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.4 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.00; NIR slit width on Servo; NIR detector response 4 s,

and, at last, the reference beam attenuator was set at 1% (the sample beam attenuator remained at 100%).

- In the range 351 – 1492 nm the measure was done with the same instrument but with different settings, which are the same for the other two monolayer samples: data interval 1 nm; common beam mask (CBM) 50%; UV/Vis slit width 5 nm; UV/Vis detector gain set on Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.4 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.0; NIR slit width on Servo, and NIR detector response 2 s.
- In the final range 1492.09 – 25000 nm the measure was done with Spectrum 3, obtained with the usual settings: SS 0.2 cm s^{-1} ; res. 4 cm^{-1} ; data interval 0.4 cm^{-1} and accumulation 128 scans.

PI-45/AI-20 (TF110-2475), section 7.4

- In the range 190 – 2000 nm the measure was done with the Lambda 1050+ instrument and here are the main characteristics: data interval 1 nm; CBM 50%; UV/Vis slit width 5 nm; UV/Vis detector gain Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.4 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.00; NIR slit width on Servo, and NIR detector response 2 s (the same prescriptions as with the measures of PI-45).
- In the range 2005 – 3140 nm the measure was done with the same instrument but different settings: data interval 5 nm; CBM 50%; UV/Vis slit width 5 nm; UV/Vis detector gain Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.2 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.00; NIR slit width on Servo, and NIR detector response 0.4 s.
- In the final range 3140.31 – 25000 nm the measure was done with Spectrum 3, obtained with the same settings as the PI samples: SS 0.2 cm s^{-1} ; res. 4 cm^{-1} ; data interval 0.4 cm^{-1} and accumulation 128 scans.

PI-45/AI-30 (TF110-2462), section 7.5

- In the range 190–2000 nm the measure was obtained with the Lambda 1050+ instrument and here are the main characteristics: data interval 1 nm; CBM 50%; UV/Vis slit width 5 nm; UV/Vis detector gain Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.4 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.00; NIR slit width on Servo, and NIR detector response 2 s (same as PI-45).
- In the range 2005 – 3225 nm the measure was obtained again with Lambda 1050+ but different settings: data interval 5 nm; CBM 50%; UV/Vis slit width 5 nm; UV/Vis detector gain Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.2 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.00; NIR slit width on Servo, and NIR detector response 0.4 s.

- In the final range 3225.39 – 25000 nm the measure was done with Spectrum 3, obtained with the same settings as the other samples, i.e.: SS 0.2 cm s⁻¹; res. 4 cm⁻¹; data interval 0.4 cm⁻¹ and accumulation 128 scans.

PI-150/AI-30 (TF110-2460), section 7.6

- In the range 190 – 350 nm the measure was done with the Lambda 1050+ instrument and the data collection settings for the measure were: data interval 2 nm; CBM 30%; UV/Vis slit width 2 nm; UV/Vis detector gain Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.4 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.00; NIR slit width on Servo; NIR detector response 4 s, and, finally, the reference beam attenuator was set at 1% (the sample beam attenuator was not set at any value).
- In the range 301 – 2500 nm the measure was done with the same instrument but different settings: data interval 1 nm; CBM 50%; UV/Vis slit width 5 nm; UV/Vis detector gain Automatic; UV/Vis detector response 0.4 s; NIR Detector Gain 1.00; NIR slit width on Servo, and NIR detector response 2.0 s.
- In the final range 2500.25 – 25000 nm the measure was done with Spectrum 3, obtained with the same settings as the other samples: SS 0.2 cm s⁻¹; res. 4 cm⁻¹; data interval 0.4 cm⁻¹ and accumulation 128 scans.

B Flowchart of the Python fit program

C The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm

This appendix is not an attempt to give an exhaustive introduction to the algorithm, and its purpose is to introduce its main aspects, in the meantime referring to the more appropriate literature the interested reader.

The Levenberg-Marquardt[79] model falls into the category of nonlinear fitting models, whose purpose is to best fit a set of data with a given model depending on some variable parameters. The algorithm needs a vector set of parameters \mathbf{a} , a_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, M$, that is M free parameters, to be fit to a given set of data. In order to accomplish the fit, a merit function is needed to be minimised, and the usual choice is the chi squared χ^2 . If we have N data points y_i , with σ_i being their statistical uncertainty⁷, and the model is given by a known function $y(x_i, \mathbf{a})$, then the χ^2 function is:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{y_i - y(x_i, \mathbf{a})}{\sigma_i} \right]^2$$

The idea is to minimise the value of χ^2 by moving in the parameter space via small displacements $\delta\mathbf{a}$: the algorithm computes $\chi^2(\mathbf{a})$, then $\chi^2(\mathbf{a} + \delta\mathbf{a})$, and evaluates whether it has increased or decreased. Then proceeds to evaluate the next $\delta\mathbf{a}$, and re-iterate the process. The way the algorithm calculates the displacements in each step is heavily dependent on this evaluation, as the algorithm, to put it in the author's words, 'performs an optimum interpolation between the Taylor series method and the gradient method', and selectively decides which mode to run the iteration based on the above evaluations. The algorithm eventually stops, either after the χ^2 has reached a local minimum, i.e. the $\Delta\chi^2$ between two iterations changes at most by a threshold typically set as $\ll 1$, or if the limit of the maximum number of iterations is reached - whose default value is usually set at about $200 \times (M + 1)$. The full set of equations in modern notation, as well as full program scripts employing the algorithm and written in C++, are available in the reference by Press et. al [80, Chap. 15.5.2].

The algorithm itself also has a built-in way to attribute a covariance matrix to the best-fit parameters. After the convergence, when the local minimum \mathbf{a} is found, one of the matrices ($\alpha = [\alpha_{kl}]$) used during the fit procedure used is evaluated.

$$\alpha_{kl} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \left[\frac{\partial y(x_i, \mathbf{a})}{\partial a_k} \frac{\partial y(x_i, \mathbf{a})}{\partial a_l} \right] \forall (k, l)$$

The correlation matrix \mathbf{C} of the best-fit parameters is then calculated by inverting the matrix, i.e. $\mathbf{C} = \alpha^{-1}$, and the uncertainties are given as square roots of the diagonal of such matrix.

⁷If the uncertainties are not available, a further parameter should be estimated and/or marginalised to properly re-scale the χ^2 , i.e. a flat uncertainty $\sigma = \sigma_i \forall i$ or a flat relative uncertainty $\varepsilon = \sigma_i/y_i$.

Two remarks can be made. The first is that the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, although very fast and combining different methods to ensure that the convergence is not slow, usually narrows the best-fit parameter set towards a local minimum of the χ^2 . This would necessarily give only local information, losing eventual other local minima or, even worse, the global minimum. In that regards a very good estimate of the initial parameters can be crucial to avoid converging towards a ‘bad’ local minimum.

Secondly, the uncertainties, as estimated from the correlation matrix (i.e. by simply square rooting the diagonal terms), can be compared to those that can be inferred from different methods. The Python routine that was employed in the thesis, `Lmfit.minimize()`, has a dedicated GitHub website (<https://lmfit.github.io/lmfit-py/fitting.html>, last visited on 05/06/2022) which explains the `Lmfit` settings in great detail. When the uncertainties seem too small to be true, it should be best to try alternatives. One way is to explore the local parameter space around the best-fit minimum to evaluate the uncertainties via χ^2 statistics approach using Bayesian inference [80, Chap. 15.6.5]. Usually, the values obtained with the two techniques are compatible, and the `Lmfit` routine offers, by tweaking the settings, the possibility to switch directly from the Levenberg-Marquardt (`method='leastsq'`, or default) to a Markov chain Monte Carlo method (`method='emcee'`) carrying out this Bayesian approach. Another possibility could be to use independent methods from the ones above, such as bootstrapping [80, Chap. 15.6.2] or other random sampling techniques.

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